

Measurement properties of the WHO Disability Assessment Schedule (WHODAS 2.0) across purposes and populations worldwide: protocol for a living systematic review

Alan R. Patlán-Hernández, Cynthia A. Lucio Garcia, Yasmeen Aldouri, Sorina Andrei, Inika Khosla, Clara Miguel, Wieneke Mokkink, Suneeta Monga, José T. Ramos, Kevin J. Samuel, Fatahiya Sumaila, Colin Sidre, Fatahiya Sumaila, Pierre-Félix Tellier, Gull Zareen, Corentin J. Gosling, Astrid Chevance, Karolin R. Krause.

GENERAL INFORMATION:

Type and method of the review: Systematic review and meta-analysis conducted following the COSMIN guideline for systematic reviews of PROMs, and the PRISMA-COSMIN guideline for reporting systematic reviews of outcome measurement instruments (OMIs).

Condition or domain being studied: This systematic review focuses on functioning and disability.

Language: English.

Country: France.

Funding sources/sponsors: This work is part of the COLIVE-MH project funded by Wellcome under contract number C-013403.

Conflicts of interest: All authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Ethical approval and consent to participate: This study synthesizes and analyzes data from already published studies, therefore ethical approval is not required.

Other registration details: None.

Dissemination plans: We plan to publish the review findings in a peer-reviewed journal.

Details of any existing review of the same topic by the same authors: None.

Current review status: Ongoing.

Additional information: None.

Protocol updated on 9th February 2026

Acknowledgement: We thank Jessie Cunningham, BA (Hons); MSt (The Hospital for Sick Children) for peer review of the submitted search strategy, and Catherine Auzimour for the project management.

1. INTRODUCTION

Functioning and disability are central outcomes for population surveys, clinical care, and research on physical and mental health. The World Health Organization Disability Assessment Schedule 2.0 (WHODAS 2.0) was developed as a generic, cross-culturally applicable measure of functioning across six domains (cognition, mobility, self-care, getting along, life activities, participation) and exists in three versions; a 36-item full version providing detailed domain-level assessment, a 12-item short version designed for brief screening, and a hybrid 12+24-item version that combines the short form with additional domain-specific items for more granular analysis (Üstün, 2010; Üstün et al., 2010). The brief 12-item version was explicitly developed to reproduce most of the 36-item version's variance (81%) while enabling rapid assessment in large samples and routine practice (Üstün, 2010; Üstün et al., 2010).

Despite their broad uptake, uncertainty remains about the measurement properties of the 12-item and the 12+24-item WHODAS 2.0 across different adult populations. Overall, research consistently demonstrates high internal consistency, good test-retest reliability, and strong criterion validity for both versions in general, clinical, and cross-cultural samples (Higgins et al., 2021; Saltychev et al., 2021; Wong et al., 2023), but questions persist about structural dimensionality (unidimensional vs. multidimensional scoring), cross-population invariance, test-retest reliability, measurement error, and responsiveness, all of which affect whether pooled scores can be validly compared or used as outcomes in trials and observational studies (Üstün et al., 2010; Holmberg et al., 2021; Saltychev et al., 2021).

Only a few systematic reviews have sought to synthesize existing evidence on the measurement properties of the WHODAS 2.0. Most of these have exclusively examined the 12-item version (Federici et al., 2017; Saltychev et al., 2021; Wong et al., 2023), and focused on populations with specific health problems such as low back pain or people with non-acute physical causes of disability (Saltychev et al., 2021; Wong et al., 2023). Notably, none of these reviews involved a quantitative synthesis of findings on measurement properties, and only one applied the COSMIN (COnsensus-based Standards for the selection of health Measurement INstruments) methodology to assess the quality of the evidence (Wong et al., 2023), which provides a standardized approach for evaluating the methodological quality of studies on the measurement properties of patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs).

The 12-item WHODAS has recently been recommended as one of the four common outcome measures to be routinely collected in mental health research by a consortium of funders and journals, with the aim of improving comparability across studies (Farber et al., 2023). This recommendation may contribute to increased uptake of the WHODAS 2.0, with an associated increase in studies examining its measurement properties. As new studies continue to emerge, it will be necessary to ensure that the evidence base on the measurement properties of the WHODAS 2.0 is regularly updated so that decisions about its use in research and clinical practice remain well informed from a global perspective. Therefore, our aim is to provide a comprehensive, methodologically rigorous, and periodically updated synthesis

of the available evidence on the measurement properties of the 12-item and 12+24-item WHODAS 2.0 across all target populations, using the COSMIN methodology. Accordingly, this review adopts a living systematic review approach, a form of evidence synthesis that is prospectively designed for ongoing updating, enabling the timely incorporation of new studies and the recurrent refinement of conclusions as the evidence base evolves.

2. OBJECTIVES

2.1. Review questions

- What are the measurement properties of the WHODAS 2.0 for measuring functioning and disability?
- What is the quality of the underlying evidence on these measurement properties?
- What are the gaps, if any, in the current evidence on the measurement properties of the WHODAS 2.0?

2.2. Objectives

1. The primary objective of this project is twofold:
 - i. to systematically identify, appraise, and synthesise all available evidence on the measurement properties, as defined by COSMIN, of the WHODAS 2.0 in measuring functioning and disability, across purposes (e.g., outcome measure of treatment effect, screening) and populations worldwide, using a living evidence synthesis approach; and
 - ii. to disseminate this evidence through an open access, accessible, regularly updated web-based platform to support researchers, clinicians, people with lived experience and other interest-holders in the informed selection and use of the scale.
2. The secondary objectives are:
 - i. to evaluate the feasibility and acceptability of implementing the WHODAS 2.0 in clinical and research settings;
 - ii. to assess the interpretability of its scores; and
 - iii. to identify and highlight key research gaps.

This systematic review follows the COLIVE-MH Master Protocol and forms part of COLIVE-MH, a broader project involving international teams of researchers in clinical epidemiology, psychiatry and anthropology and co-researchers with lived experience. This project aims to develop a periodically updated platform on the measurement properties of four patient-reported outcome measures recommended by the Common Measures in Mental Health Science Initiative (CMMHS): WHODAS-12, GAD-7, PHQ-9, and RCADS-25.

3. METHODS

3.1. Study design and methodological and reporting guidelines:

This protocol will be prospectively registered on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>). Any protocol deviations or amendments will be documented in the Supplementary Materials of future peer-reviewed publications issued from this living systematic review.

This protocol and the resulting review will adhere to the following guidelines for individual studies and evidence base appraisal, and evidence synthesis reporting:

- **PRESS** (Peer Review of Electronic Search Strategies) (McGowan et al., 2016), for the development and peer review of the search strategy.
- The systematic review will be conducted according to the **COSMIN 2.0 guidelines** (Mokkink et al., 2024), which provide recommendations for the synthesis and appraisal of evidence on measurement properties.
- The **Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Diagnostic Test Accuracy** (Deeks et al., 2023), and the **QUADAS-2** (Quality Assessment of Diagnostic Accuracy Studies) for diagnostic accuracy studies (Tomlinson et al., 2025), will be consulted for additional guidance when assessing the performance of the WHODAS 2.0 as a screening or diagnostic tool.
- This protocol, and the publication of results from the living systematic review will follow the **PRISMA-P** (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis Protocols) (Page et al., 2021), the **PRISMA-COSMIN** guideline for reporting systematic reviews of outcome measurement instruments (OMIs) (Elsman et al., 2024), and the **PRISMA-LSR** (PRISMA extension for living systematic reviews) (Akl et al., 2024).
- The involvement of experts with lived experience will be reported following the **GRIPP-2 framework** (Staniszewska et al., 2017).

3.2. Formulation of the research question

Construct: Functioning and disability as defined by the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF).

Population: During the mapping stage, no restriction on the type of population, age, gender, sex, nationality, language, country, or settings will be applied.

Instrument: Self- or interviewer-administered version of the World Health Organization Disability Assessment Schedule 2.0 (WHODAS 2.0).

Measurement properties: Evidence on the WHODAS 2.0 measurement properties (based on the COSMIN framework, with adaptations) in measuring functioning and disability including:

1. Content validity
2. Structural validity
3. Internal consistency
4. Cross-cultural validity / measurement invariance
5. Reliability
6. Measurement error
7. Criterion validity
8. Diagnostic and screening accuracy
9. Hypothesis testing (convergent, concurrent validity)
10. Responsiveness

Other properties:

11. Feasibility
12. Interpretability
13. Acceptability

Study design(s): We will include primary studies irrespective of their design, as eligibility will be based on the presence of evaluable evidence on measurement properties rather than on the type of study design.

3.3. Pilot feasibility study

Prior to developing the present protocol, we conducted a pilot study to assess the feasibility of the project and to inform key methodological decisions. Detailed information on the pilot search strategies, screening procedures, results, and methodological insights is provided in **Appendix A**.

The pilot involved running preliminary searches in PubMed (from database inception to 3 December 2025) using an initial version of the search strategy that was then compared with search strategies from previous systematic reviews on the WHODAS (Federici et al., 2017; Saltychev et al., 2021) or using the COSMIN Framework (Wong et al., 2023; Meng et al., 2025), in order to assess the sensibility of our search strategy and the feasibility of the screening process. As the number of retrieved records was moderate across all tested strategies, we adopted the simplified version (using only WHODAS-related terms) in order to ensure comprehensive coverage. The search yielded 1,649 records, which were reduced to 1,645 records after duplicate removal. Two reviewers independently screened the titles and abstracts of a random sample of 200 records. Of these, 14 studies (7%) were selected for full-text assessment, and 6 studies (43% of the screened sample) ultimately met the eligibility criteria for inclusion in the systematic review. Based on these results, we would anticipate that approximately 400

studies would undergo full-text screening, of which about 172 would be expected to be included in the systematic review. Nevertheless, findings from the pilot study were also used to refine the search strategies, eligibility criteria, and screening and data extraction procedures for the final review protocol. Notably, the pilot study applied more restrictive inclusion criteria, limited to publications involving general population samples or samples with mental health or substance use disorders. In contrast, the present systematic review protocol adopts broader criteria and includes studies conducted in any population.

3.4. Eligibility criteria

We will include peer-reviewed empirical studies published from 1st of January 1995 until January 20th 2026 if they meet all the inclusion criteria. The start date was selected to ensure identification of studies using the WHODAS II published during the WHODAS 2.0 development period and prior to the publication of the WHODAS 2.0 development paper and manual in 2010 (Üstün et al., 2010). Searches will be updated six months after the initial search and every three months thereafter.

Inclusion criteria

Construct of interest

We consider functioning and disability as constructs of interest. For both constructs we consider the definition from the ICF, which conceptualizes functioning as a dynamic interaction between an individual's health condition, environmental factors, and personal factors. Within this framework, functioning and disability are understood as umbrella terms, capturing the positive and negative dimensions of human functioning from biological, individual, and social perspectives (WHO, 2013).

Functioning encompasses body functions, body structures, activities, and participation, representing the positive aspects of the interaction between a person (with a health condition) and their contextual factors (environmental and personal). In contrast, disability encompasses impairments, activity limitations, and participation restrictions, reflecting the negative aspects of the same interaction (WHO, 2013).

Importantly, the ICF places functioning and disability within the context of health, and therefore does not account for circumstances arising solely from socioeconomic or cultural factors (WHO, 2013).

Studies in which the WHODAS 2.0 is used to measure a construct that is broader than, different from, or insufficiently specified relative to its originally intended construct will be excluded from the systematic synthesis stage. While functioning and disability represent the constructs that the WHODAS 2.0 was originally designed to measure, some studies use it as a proxy for general health status, quality of life, wellbeing, or treatment outcomes. At the evidence mapping stage, such studies will be retained and tagged accordingly to transparently document how the instruments are used in the literature.

Population

- No restrictions on population characteristics. Studies including individuals of any age, gender or sex, nationality, language, country, cultural background, or setting will be eligible.
- Both clinical (physical/somatic or mental health) and non-clinical populations will be included.

Type of instrument

We will identify and include studies of all three versions of the self-administered and interviewer-administered WHODAS 2.0 (36-item, 12-item, and 12+24-item) in any language. For systematic appraisal and qualitative and quantitative evidence synthesis, we will first prioritize studies on the 12-item and the 12+24-item versions.

- Studies on the WHODAS 2.0 and any modified versions will be eligible for inclusion only if the original item structure of the instrument is preserved. For example, this requires maintaining the 12-item or 36-item WHODAS 2.0 with its original six-domain structure (cognition, mobility, self-care, getting along, life activities, and participation), even in culturally adapted versions (e.g., translated or culturally adapted WHODAS 2.0 forms) or population-specific versions (such as youth or condition-specific adaptations).
- Studies using modified versions of the WHODAS 2.0 will be included only if the original item content is preserved. Modifications to the item wording will be allowed if the meaning and content of the item remains unchanged. These modifications will be explicitly recorded and considered in the data extraction and synthesis.
- Studies using the self- or interviewer-administered version of the WHODAS 2.0 administered by any medium, such as electronic, paper, or read-aloud formats (e.g., by telephone) will be included as long as the participant is the main respondent, and there is no judgment or influence beyond standard guidance (e.g., guided interpretation). Populations with severe impairment will be included if individuals can independently understand, interpret and respond to the instrument.

Measurement properties

We define the measurement properties according to the COSMIN taxonomy (Mokkink et al., 2009, 2024), with adaptations. Although not measurement properties per se, feasibility, interpretability, and acceptability of the WHODAS 2.0 will also be included as other properties and be considered as outcomes of interest in this systematic review due to their practical relevance. Definitions of all measurement properties and other properties are listed in **Table 1** and **Table 2**, and examples of commonly reported analyses and indicators are operationalized in **Appendix B**.

- We will include peer-reviewed studies in which at least one stated objective is to evaluate one or more measurement properties and that report, in the methods or results section, findings on the assessment of at least one measurement property (including feasibility, interpretability, and

acceptability) of either the self-administered or interviewer-administered versions of the WHODAS 2.0.

- Studies will be included only when results are reported or described in sufficient detail in the methods or results section.
- Studies using any statistical methods of analysis will be included (e.g. Classic test theory, Item Response theory).

Study design

Eligibility will be determined by the presence of evaluable evidence on any measurement property rather than by study design alone.

- Primary studies with any design (including cross-sectional, longitudinal, cohort, validation, and instrument development studies) appraising at least one measurement property of the self- or the interviewer-administered version of the WHODAS 2.0 will be considered eligible.
- Trials (randomised/non-randomised) will also be included if they have investigated, as an ancillary objective, at least one measurement property.
- Qualitative studies in which participants from any population (e.g., patients with lived experience of depression, clinicians, caregivers, or members of the general population) will be also included if they report evidence on any of the measurement properties (e.g., content validity, development paper) or any of the other properties of the instrument (i.e., feasibility, interpretability, and acceptability).

Table 1. Definition of the measurement properties of measurement tools.

Measurement property	Definition
1. Content validity	The degree to which the content of a PROM is an adequate reflection of the construct to be measured.
2. Structural validity	The degree to which the scores of a PROM are an adequate reflection of the dimensionality of the construct to be measured.
3. Internal consistency	The degree of the interrelatedness among the items.
4. Cross-cultural validity / measurement invariance	The degree to which the performance of the items on a translated or culturally adapted PROM are an adequate reflection of the performance of the items of the original version of the PROM.
5. Reliability	The proportion of the total variance in the measurements which is due to “true” ¹ differences between patients.

6. Measurement error	The systematic and random error of a patient's score that is not attributed to true changes in the construct to be measured.
7. Criterion validity	The degree to which the scores of a PROM are an adequate reflection of a "gold standard".
8. Diagnostic and screening accuracy	The ability of the PROM to correctly classify study participants, as having the target disorder or not. In most cases, that information will be relevant when the PROM is considered for diagnostic reasons (to identify the disorder that most likely is responsible for the signs and symptoms of the patient) or for screening purposes (to identify patients with unrecognised depression).
9. Hypothesis testing for construct validity	The degree to which the scores of a PROM are consistent with hypotheses (regarding relationships to scores of other instruments, or differences between relevant groups) based on the assumption that the PROM validly measures the construct to be measured.
10. Responsiveness	The ability of a PROM to detect change over time in the construct to be measured.

The definitions of the measurement properties are based on the COSMIN taxonomy, extracted from the COSMIN 2.0 guidelines (Mokkink et al., 2024). The Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Diagnostic Test Accuracy will be used where appropriate to supplement the COSMIN guidance (Deeks et al., 2023).

¹ The word "true" must be seen in the context of the CTT, which states that any observation is composed of two components – a true score and error associated with the observation. "True" is the average score that would be obtained if the scale were given an infinite number of times. It refers only to the consistency of the score, and not to its accuracy (Streiner & Norman, 2008).

Table 2. Definition of other properties of measurement tools.

Property	Definition
11. Feasibility*	Ease of application of the PROM in its intended context of use, given constraints such as time or money.
12. Interpretability*	The degree to which one can assign qualitative meaning, that is, clinical or commonly understood connotations, to a PROM's quantitative scores or change in scores.
13. Acceptability	How respondents perceive the experience of completing the scale, e.g., perceived intrusiveness, burden, potential harms or benefits.

*The definitions are based on the COSMIN taxonomy, extracted from the COSMIN 2.0 guidelines (Mokkink et al., 2024). Feasibility and interpretability are not considered a measurement property, but an important aspect when selecting measurement instruments.

Acceptability was added specifically to this project and the definition will be refined according to the literature identified during the systematic review.

Exclusion criteria

The following exclusion criteria will be applied:

1. We will exclude non-peer reviewed records, such as conference abstracts, posters, dissertations, short communications, grey literature; Open Science Framework publications, and university repositories.
2. Studies in which the WHODAS 2.0 is used solely as a comparator to evaluate another instrument, or only as a predictor, grouping variable, or prevalence estimator, without any examination of the measurement properties of the WHODAS 2.0 itself, will be excluded.
3. Case studies will be excluded because they do not provide enough information to evaluate measurement properties.

Some studies that do not meet the eligibility criteria will be systematically identified and tagged under one or more predefined categories throughout the whole screening process. Although these studies fall outside the primary scope of the present review, they may still be relevant for parallel projects, methodological insights, or contextual interpretation of the literature. Tagging allows us to maintain a structured overview of the broader literature and to identify connections, gaps, and complementary bodies of work. For example, systematic reviews on the measurement properties of the WHODAS 2.0 can help in identifying additional eligible studies and to inform discussion of the existing evidence base. The following tags will be used:

1. Studies using the clinician version (when defined or referred as a Clinician-Reported Outcome Measure (ClinROM)) of the WHODAS.
2. **Effects of the scale:** Studies investigating the effects of administering the WHODAS 2.0 on individuals, groups, or settings (e.g., psychological impact, behavioural consequences, or social effects), as these studies focus on the consequences of measurement rather than on examining measurement properties. These studies will be integrated in an ancillary scoping review.
3. **Educational or implementation-focused studies:** Studies providing conceptual, methodological, or implementation-oriented insights into the use of the WHODAS 2.0 (educational or implementation-focused studies), for example studies examining barriers and facilitators to uptake of the tool by clinicians, training strategies for clinicians, or integration of the WHODAS 2.0 into routine care or digital systems. They will be used to guide the website interface of the platform.
4. **Cross-walk or score equivalence studies:** Studies using the WHODAS 2.0 alongside other measures with the sole purpose to generate cross-walks, linking functions or score equivalence across instruments. The primary focus of these studies is on mathematical comparability across

scales rather than on assessing the performance of the WHODAS 2.0 itself (e.g., a score of 6 in WHODAS = 5 in the Sheehan Disability Scale (SDS)).

5. **Unclear or mismatched construct use:** Studies using the instrument to measure different or insufficiently specified constructs than functioning and disability.
6. **Systematic reviews and meta-analyses:** Systematic reviews and meta-analyses of measurement properties of the WHODAS 2.0.
7. **Studies examining modified versions** of the WHODAS 2.0 in which the content of the original items has been modified. This includes modifications to response options (e.g., alternative response formats), scoring algorithms (e.g., alternative ways of summing the items into a total score), cut-off thresholds (e.g., exploring different thresholds than the originally validated), instructions for completion (e.g., more developed or specific instructions than the originally provided) or recall period (e.g., experience in the last week instead of the last two weeks).

3.5. Searched databases and search strategy

The following electronic databases will be searched: MEDLINE via PubMed, CINAHL via EBSCO, Embase via Elsevier, Web of Science via Clarivate, PsycInfo via EBSCO. Grey literature will not be searched. Although grey literature can provide relevant content to increase the comprehensiveness of a review and reduce publication bias, the systematic review aims to map and synthesize peer reviewed studies only to ensure the feasibility and quality of the overall project. We acknowledge that restricting inclusion to peer-reviewed literature may result in the omission of locally produced knowledge, rare language adaptations, and context-specific validation studies that are not indexed in major international bibliographic databases. Searches will be conducted for studies published between 1 January 1995 and 20th January 2026. An update will be performed on 1 July 2026, followed by additional updates at 3-month intervals.

The search strategy was developed by the review team and reviewed and adapted for all bibliographic databases by two information specialists from the Université Paris Cité. The full strategy was independently peer-reviewed by an external information specialist from the Hospital for Sick Children (SickKids), Toronto, in accordance with the PRESS 2015 guidelines (McGowan et al., 2016), prior to execution. The detailed final search strategy is provided in **Appendix C**.

In addition, the reference lists of included primary studies and relevant systematic reviews will be screened to identify any additional eligible studies. Citation tracking tools (e.g. Research Rabbit <https://www.researchrabbit.ai/>) may also be used to identify related studies, including forward and backward citations of included articles.

3.6. Screening procedure

Records will be imported into the Sustainable Knowledge (SK) platform, developed by Epistemonikos as part of its end-to-end system for reference deduplication and management (<https://www.skplatform.org/>) (Rada et al., 2020). The platform will also be used for the screening process. Each record will be screened in duplicate by two reviewers based on titles and abstracts to identify potentially eligible studies. Discrepancies will be solved by a third reviewer. Full-text articles will then be independently reviewed by both reviewers to determine final inclusion in the systematic review.

Disagreements at any stage will be resolved through discussion between the reviewers, and, if necessary, by consultation with a third reviewer. The study selection process will be documented and reported in accordance with the PRISMA 2020 guidelines, using a PRISMA flow diagram and a list of studies excluded at the full-text stage with the reasons for exclusion.

3.7. Sequential methodological approach

Data extraction and synthesis will be organized in a workflow of two sequential and complementary phases:

Phase A: Living mapping of the measurement properties evidence base and data extraction

To systematically identify all studies reporting one or more measurement properties of the WHODAS 2.0 and to map their key characteristics, including study design, instrument features, participant characteristics, and the measurement properties assessed. This living mapping will populate the COLIVE-MH living platform and will be regularly updated.

Phase B: Living evidence syntheses of measurement properties

To conduct COSMIN-guided systematic reviews of methodologically coherent subsets of the evidence base, such as defined populations or intended uses of the instrument. Each review will synthesize findings, assess risk of bias, and evaluate the certainty of the evidence for the WHODAS 2.0 within the specific context under evaluation. The resulting syntheses will be integrated into the living platform, enabling comparison and aggregation of evidence across contexts. Potential areas for improvement of the WHODAS 2.0 will also be identified through this review.

3.8. Phase A: Living mapping of the evidence base

Data extraction: All studies meeting the inclusion criteria after full-text screening will undergo a structured data extraction within the Epistemonikos end-to-end system. Data extraction for each record will also be performed by two reviewers independently. All reviewers involved in the screening process will be trained using 10% of the included studies to ensure methodological alignment, completeness, and consistency across reviewers. The data extraction codebook, with detailed definitions for each

variable, including the measurement properties, for the living mapping phase is provided in **Appendix**

D. For each study, data will be collected across eight broad categories:

- A. **Study metadata:** Study ID, year of publication, journal, DOI, etc.
- B. **Study characteristics:** Design of the study, inclusion criteria with threshold, etc.
- C. **Characteristics of the WHODAS-12:** Exact version of the instrument used, administration mode (self-administered, read-aloud, etc.), format (Paper/pencil, online, etc.), different languages and cultural adaptations (e.g., translated to Arabic), or other adaptations (e.g., Adolescent version), etc.
- D. **Purpose of use** for which the properties of the WHODAS-12 are being examined (outcome assessment, screening/diagnostic).
- E. **Participant characteristics:** Sociodemographic (age, gender/sex, and country, specific demographics such as prisoners, migrants, etc.) and clinical characteristics (e.g., general population, physical illness, mental health condition), etc.
- F. **Measurement properties:** At this stage, we will only identify and report which measurement properties are examined in each article; articles will be classified on that basis. Measurement properties will be classified based on the analyses and statistics reported in the primary studies, following COSMIN guidance. Definitions of all measurement properties are listed in Table 1, and examples of commonly reported analyses and indicators are operationalized in Appendix B.
- G. **Other properties of the instrument:** Studies reporting evidence on feasibility, interpretability, and/or acceptability of the scale will be also classified accordingly.
- H. **Involvement of contributors with lived experiences:** We will extract information on whether individuals with lived experiences actively contributed to each included study, beyond their role as study participants.

The data extraction form will be pilot tested on a subset of random included studies to ensure completeness and consistency. In the context of a living systematic review, both the extraction form and the dataset will be updated on an ongoing basis as new evidence emerges.

Data synthesis: The data extraction of this phase will allow us to map the available evidence and to inform the organization of Phase B. The data will be analysed using descriptive statistics, and all outputs will be displayed in the open-access platform.

3.9. Phase B: Evidence synthesis of the WHODAS 2.0 properties

Phase B will synthesize evidence on the measurement properties of the WHODAS 2.0 in accordance with the COSMIN guidelines. We will first extract and examine the characteristics of the WHODAS 2.0 from its original development and validation studies to define its intended measurement scope and to inform the subsequent assessment of content validity.

Building on the results of the living evidence mapping conducted in Phase A, we will conduct sequenced COSMIN-guided systematic reviews of measurement properties in diverse population defined by clinical and/or sociodemographic relevance (for example, measurement properties of the WHODAS 2.0 in individuals with depression or with drug or substance use disorders). All living systematic reviews conducted within this project will use harmonized methodologies, enabling meaningful comparison and integration of findings.

The sequencing of reviews will be informed by the Phase A (evidence base mapping) and by input from project collaborators, including scientific with diverse expertise and lived experts.

Within each review, we will extract data on all reported measurement properties of the WHODAS 2.0 and assess the methodological quality of included primary studies using the COSMIN criteria for good measurement properties. The evidence base will be synthesized, including quantitative pooling where appropriate, and the certainty of evidence will be assessed using GRADE. Finally, based on the review findings, we will identify remaining gaps in the evidence base regarding the measurement properties of the WHODAS 2.0.

Further methodological details of Phase B are provided in the Master Protocol of the COLIVE-MH project.

3.10. Living systematic review methodology

This review is designed as a living systematic review. The literature searches will be updated 6 months after the initial search to allow sufficient time for the initial screening and data extraction. Thereafter, updates will be conducted at 3-month intervals. However, frequency of updates may be adapted based on the amount of evidence and the available resources. At each update, newly identified records will undergo title and abstract screening followed by full-text assessment, using the same eligibility and exclusion criteria applied in the initial review. Studies deemed eligible during these updates will be included in data extraction and synthesis of Phases A and B, as well as in the methodological appraisal and risk of bias assessment conducted in Phase B, following the same standardized methodological guidance used in the initial review. Every update will be disseminated in partnership through the Epistemonikos Platform for Interactive Evidence Synthesis (<https://ies.epistemonikos.org/home>).

The review is planned to remain in living mode for a period of 2 years starting from the date of the first search. Retirement from the living mode will be considered based on prespecified criteria, including stability of conclusions across updates, or reduced relevance of the review question. If none of these criteria are met at the end of the planned period, the need for continuing the updates will be reassessed.

3.11. Ethics and Dissemination

As this study synthesizes existing literature, no ethical approval will be required. The protocol will be prospectively registered on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>), and all protocol deviations will be transparently reported in the Supplementary Materials of the respective peer-reviewed publications issued from this living systematic review. Findings will be disseminated through peer-reviewed publications, national and international conference presentations. Results will be hosted on an open-access living evidence platform which development will be described elsewhere.

3.12. Lived experiences engagement

We consider the engagement of individuals with lived experiences of mental disorders to be central to this project. Although the evidence on the measurement properties of WHODAS 2.0 will be reviewed across all populations, particular emphasis will be placed on its use among individuals with mental health and substance-use disorders. In addition, the other measurement tools targeted in this project are designed to assess mental health symptoms through self-reported evaluations.

As of 9th February 2026, the engagement plan is still under development in collaboration with people with lived experiences from different countries and diverse backgrounds. This protocol was developed with two co-researchers with lived experiences and a background in psychology, and is currently under review by three experts with lived experiences and with a background in anthropology. The next update of this protocol will detail the engagement procedures to be implemented at each stage of the living systematic review.

4. REFERENCES

- Abdin, E., Seet, V., Jeyagurunathan, A., Tan, S. C., Mohmad Khalid, M. I. S., Mok, Y. M., Verma, S. K., & Subramaniam, M. (2025). Responsiveness and minimal important differences of common disability measures in people with depression and anxiety disorders. *Frontiers in Rehabilitation Sciences*, *6*, 1556390. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fresc.2025.1556390>
- Abdin, E., Seet, V., Jeyagurunathan, A., Tan, S. C., Mok, Y. M., Verma, S., Lee, E. S., & Subramaniam, M. (2023). Validation of the 12-item World Health Organization Disability Assessment Schedule 2.0 in individuals with schizophrenia, depression, anxiety, and diabetes in Singapore. *PLOS ONE*, *18*(11), e0294908. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0294908>
- Akl, E. A., Khabsa, J., Iannizzi, C., Piechotta, V., Kahale, L. A., Barker, J. M., McKenzie, J. E., Page, M. J., & Skoetz, N. (2024). Extension of the PRISMA 2020 statement for living systematic reviews (PRISMA-LSR): Checklist and explanation. *BMJ*, *387*, e079183. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj-2024-079183>
- Ämmälä, A.-J., & Taimela, S. (2026). The ability of EQ-5D-5L and WHODAS 2.0 to detect relevant change in primary health care outpatients with diagnosed depression. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, *394*, 120541. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2025.120541>
- Amoretti, S., Crespín, J. J., Corrales, M., Torrent, C., Clougher, D., Biel, S., Ramos-Sayalero, C., Ibáñez, P., Mestres, F., Fadeuilhe, C., Richarte, V., & Ramos-Quiroga, J. A. (2025). Validation of the 12-item World Health Organization Disability Assessment Schedule (WHODAS 2.0) in adults with attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder. *BJPsych Open*, *11*(6), e257. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjo.2025.10873>
- Cavero, V., Diez-Canseco, F., Bernabé-Ortiz, A., Gamboa Galvez, L., Cusihuaman-Lope, N., Sanchez-Monge, M., & Lazo-Porras, M. (2025). Co-prioritization of mental health recovery outcomes and scales for community mental health centers in Peru. *BMC Health Services Research*, *25*(1), 1162. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-025-13140-7>
- Cheng, S., Hou, C., Wu, Y., Du, X., Liu, H., Li, R., Lei, S., Yue, X., & Guo, Y. (2025). Psychometric comparison and score conversion between World Health Organization Disability Assessment

- Schedule 2.0 and activities of daily living scales in community-dwelling older adults. *European Geriatric Medicine*, 16(6), 2141-2151. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41999-025-01306-9>
- Deeks, J., & Bossuyt, P. (2023). Chapter 2 : Evaluating medical tests. In *Cochrane handbook for systematic reviews of diagnostic test accuracy*. Cochrane. <https://training.cochrane.org/handbook-diagnostic-test-accuracy/current> (Édition originale 2023)
- Deeks, J., Bossuyt, P., Leeflang, M., & Takwoingi, Y. (2023). *Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Diagnostic Test Accuracy. Version 2.0*. Cochrane. <https://training.cochrane.org/handbook-diagnostic-test-accuracy/current>
- Elsman, E. B. M., Mookink, L. B., Terwee, C. B., Beaton, D., Gagnier, J. J., Tricco, A. C., Baba, A., Butcher, N. J., Smith, M., Hofstetter, C., Lee Aiyegbusi, O., Berardi, A., Farmer, J., Haywood, K. L., Krause, K. R., Markham, S., Mayo-Wilson, E., Mehdipour, A., Ricketts, J., ... Offringa, M. (2024). Guideline for reporting systematic reviews of outcome measurement instruments (OMIs) : PRISMA-COSMIN for OMIs 2024. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*, 173, 111422. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2024.111422>
- Farber, G. K., Gage, S., Kemmer, D., & White, R. (2023). Common measures in mental health : A joint initiative by funders and journals. *The Lancet Psychiatry*, 10(6), 465-470. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366\(23\)00139-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366(23)00139-6)
- Federici, S., Bracalenti, M., Meloni, F., & Luciano, J. V. (2017). World Health Organization disability assessment schedule 2.0 : An international systematic review. *Disability and Rehabilitation*, 39(23), 2347-2380. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09638288.2016.1223177>
- Ferro, M. A., Elgie, M., Dol, M., & Basque, D. (2023). Measurement invariance of the 12-item self-administered World Health Organization Disability Assessment Schedule (WHODAS) 2.0 across early and late adolescents in Canada. *Disability and Rehabilitation*, 45(19), 3118-3124. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09638288.2022.2118867>
- Habtamu, K., Alem, A., Medhin, G., Fekadu, A., & Hanlon, C. (2018). Functional impairment among people with severe and enduring mental disorder in rural Ethiopia : A cross-sectional study.

Social Psychiatry and Psychiatric Epidemiology, 53(8), 803-814.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00127-018-1546-6>

Higgins, A. M., Neto, A. S., Bailey, M., Barrett, J., Bellomo, R., Cooper, D. J., Gabbe, B., Linke, N., Myles, P. S., Paton, M., Philpot, S., Shulman, M., Young, M., & Hodgson, C. L. (2021). The psychometric properties and minimal clinically important difference for disability assessment using WHODAS 2.0 in critically ill patients. *Critical Care and Resuscitation*, 23(1), 103-112. <https://doi.org/10.51893/2021.1.OA10>

Holmberg, C., Gremyr, A., Torgerson, J., & Mehlig, K. (2021). Clinical validity of the 12-item WHODAS-2.0 in a naturalistic sample of outpatients with psychotic disorders. *BMC Psychiatry*, 21(1), 147. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-021-03101-9>

Kimber, M., Rehm, J., & Ferro, M. A. (2015). Measurement Invariance of the WHODAS 2.0 in a Population-Based Sample of Youth. *PLOS ONE*, 10(11), e0142385. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0142385>

McDonald, E. J., BHSc, C. B., BKin, S. I. K., Perlman, C. M., & Ferro, M. A. (2023). *Psychometric properties and informant agreement of the WHODAS 2.0 in youth with mental disorder*.

McGowan, J., Sampson, M., Salzwedel, D. M., Cogo, E., Foerster, V., & Lefebvre, C. (2016). PRESS Peer Review of Electronic Search Strategies : 2015 Guideline Statement. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*, 75, 40-46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2016.01.021>

Meng, R., Huang, M., Miller, C. B., Fong, D. Y. T., Gregory, A. M., Pakpour, A. H., Dzierzewski, J. M., Henry, A. L., Voinescu, B. I., Yang, N., Ma, H., Luo, Y., Lau, E. Y. Y., Spruyt, K., & Espie, C. A. (2025). Global perspectives on the Sleep Condition Indicator for DSM-5 insomnia disorder : A COSMIN and STARD systematic review of psychometric and diagnostic performance. *BMC Medicine*, 23(1), 542. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12916-025-04285-7>

Mihretu, A., Aleyan, S., Schmider, J., Hanlon, C., Lund, C., Araya, R., White, A., & Habtamu, K. (2025). Evaluating the reliability and validity of the 12-item WHODAS 2.0 among people with mental health conditions in seven low- and middle-income countries : Analysis of secondary data. *BJPpsych Open*, 11(6), e231. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjo.2025.10778>

- Mokkink, L. B., Elsmann, E. B. M., & Terwee, C. B. (2024). COSMIN guideline for systematic reviews of patient-reported outcome measures version 2.0. *Quality of Life Research*, *33*(11), 2929-2939. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11136-024-03761-6>
- Mokkink, L. B., Terwee, C. B., Stratford, P. W., Alonso, J., Patrick, D. L., Riphagen, I., Knol, D. L., Bouter, L. M., & De Vet, H. C. W. (2009). Evaluation of the methodological quality of systematic reviews of health status measurement instruments. *Quality of Life Research*, *18*(3), 313-333. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11136-009-9451-9>
- Page, M. J., McKenzie, J. E., Bossuyt, P. M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T. C., Mulrow, C. D., Shamseer, L., Tetzlaff, J. M., Akl, E. A., Brennan, S. E., Chou, R., Glanville, J., Grimshaw, J. M., Hróbjartsson, A., Lalu, M. M., Li, T., Loder, E. W., Mayo-Wilson, E., McDonald, S., ... Moher, D. (2021). The PRISMA 2020 statement: An updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ*, *n71*. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n71>
- Rada, G., Pérez, D., Araya-Quintanilla, F., Ávila, C., Bravo-Soto, G., Bravo-Jeria, R., Cánepa, A., Capurro, D., Castro-Gutiérrez, V., Contreras, V., Edwards, J., Faúndez, J., Garrido, D., Jiménez, M., Llovet, V., Lobos, D., Madrid, F., Morel-Marambio, M., Mendoza, A., ... Zilleruelo-Ramos, R. (2020). Epistemonikos: A comprehensive database of systematic reviews for health decision-making. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, *20*(1), 286. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-020-01157-x>
- Risal, A., Kunwar, D., Karki, E., Adhikari, S. P., Bimali, I., Shrestha, B., Khadka, S., & Holen, A. (2021). Adapting World Health Organization Disability Assessment Schedule 2.0 for Nepal. *BMC Psychology*, *9*(1), 45. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40359-021-00550-5>
- Saltychev, M., Katajapuu, N., Bärlund, E., & Laimi, K. (2021). Psychometric properties of 12-item self-administered World Health Organization disability assessment schedule 2.0 (WHODAS 2.0) among general population and people with non-acute physical causes of disability – systematic review. *Disability and Rehabilitation*, *43*(6), 789-794. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09638288.2019.1643416>
- Staniszewska, S., Brett, J., Simera, I., Seers, K., Mockford, C., Goodlad, S., Altman, D. G., Moher, D., Barber, R., Denegri, S., Entwistle, A., Littlejohns, P., Morris, C., Suleman, R., Thomas, V., &

- Tysall, C. (2017). GRIPP2 reporting checklists : Tools to improve reporting of patient and public involvement in research. *BMJ*, j3453. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.j3453>
- Streiner, D. L., & Norman, G. L. (2008). *Health measurement scales : A practical guide to their development and use*. (4th Edition). Oxford University Press.
- Terwee, C. B., Jansma, E. P., Riphagen, I. I., & De Vet, H. C. W. (2009). Development of a methodological PubMed search filter for finding studies on measurement properties of measurement instruments. *Quality of Life Research*, 18(8), 1115-1123. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11136-009-9528-5>
- Theotokatos, G., Escorpizo, R., Angelopoulos, T. J., Chrysagis, N. K., Bickenbach, J., Venieri, A., Karteroliotis, K., Grammatopoulou, E., & Skordilis, E. (2023). Psychometric Properties of the 12-Item World Health Organization Disability Assessment Schedule (WHODAS 2.0), Greek Version : A Cross-Sectional Study on Applicants of Welfare Benefits. *Cureus*. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.48588>
- Tomlinson, E., Yang, B., Davenport, C. F., Rutjes, A. WS., Mallett, S., & Whiting, P. F. (2025). Piloting QUADAS-3 : A revised tool for the quality assessment of diagnostic accuracy studies. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*, 188, 111983. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2025.111983>
- Tompke, B. K., Tang, J., Oltean, I. I., Buchan, M. C., Reaume, S. V., & Ferro, M. A. (2020). Measurement Invariance of the WHODAS 2.0 Across Youth With and Without Physical or Mental Conditions. *Assessment*, 27(7), 1490-1501. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1073191118816435>
- Üstün, T. B. (Éd.). (2010). *Measuring health and disability : Manual for WHO Disability Assessment Schedule WHODAS 2.0*. World Health Organization.
- Üstün, T. B., Chatterji, S., Kostanjsek, N., Rehm, J., Kennedy, C., Epping-Jordan, J., Saxena, S., von Korf, M., & Pull, C. (2010). Developing the World Health Organization Disability Assessment Schedule 2.0. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*, 88(11), 815-823. <https://doi.org/10.2471/BLT.09.067231>
- Wada, R., Fujiwara, M., Yamada, Y., Nakaya, N., Fujimori, M., So, R., Kodama, M., Higuchi, Y., Kakeda, K., Uchitomi, Y., Yamada, N., & Inagaki, M. (2021). *Validity and Reliability of the*

Japanese Version of the 12-item Self-administered World Health Organization Disability Assessment Schedule (WHODAS) 2.0 in Patients with Schizophrenia.

- Weeks, M., Garber, B. G., & Zamorski, M. A. (2016). Disability and Mental Disorders in the Canadian Armed Forces. *The Canadian Journal of Psychiatry, 61*(1_suppl), 56S-63S. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0706743716628853>
- WHO (Éd.). (2013). *How to use the ICF: A practical manual for using the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF).Exposure draft for comment.* World Health Organization.
- Wong, J. J., DeSouza, A., Hogg-Johnson, S., De Groote, W., Southerst, D., Belchos, M., Lemeunier, N., Alexopoulos, S., Varmazyar, H., Mior, S. A., Stern, P. J., Nordin, M. C., Taylor-Vaisey, A., Cieza, A., & Côté, P. (2023). Measurement Properties and Minimal Important Change of the World Health Organization Disability Assessment Schedule 2.0 in Persons With Low Back Pain: A Systematic Review. *Archives of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation, 104*(2), 287-301. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmr.2022.06.005>
- Zhou, W., Liu, Q., Yu, Y., Xiao, S., Chen, L., Khoshnood, K., & Zheng, S. (2020). Proxy reliability of the 12-item world health organization disability assessment schedule II among adult patients with mental disorders. *Quality of Life Research, 29*(8), 2219-2229. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11136-020-02474-w>

APPENDICES

Appendix A. Pilot feasibility study for the WHODAS 2.0 systematic review

Purpose of the pilot study

To refine the methodology of the living systematic review, we conducted a pilot study aimed at identifying the most effective approaches for screening and extracting the evidence on the measurement properties of the World Health Organization Disability Assessment Schedule 2.0 (WHODAS 2.0). The pilot study was designed to assess the feasibility of the proposed search strategy, screening workflow, inclusion and exclusion criteria, and test data extraction procedures, in accordance with COSMIN recommendations (Mokkink et al., 2024).

Scoping work and development of the search strategy

We first reviewed existing systematic reviews of the WHODAS 2.0 or using the COSMIN Framework to examine how previous authors structured their search strategies, selected and operationalized search terms, and reported measurement properties. Particular attention was paid to the application of methodological frameworks such as COSMIN and QUADAS. Insights gained from this scoping exercise informed the development of our initial COSMIN-based search strategy. A comparison between our initial search strategy and those used in previous systematic reviews is presented in **Table A**.

Table A. Comparison of search strategies.

Block	Our initial search strategy	Search strategy used in review by Meng et al 2025	Search strategy used in review by Saltychev et al 2021	Search strategy used in review by Federici et al 2017
Population	<p>("adult"[MeSH Terms] OR adult*[tiab] OR "adolescent"[MeSH Terms] OR adolescen*[tiab] OR teen*[tiab] OR youth*[tiab] OR "young people"[tiab] OR elderly[tiab] OR geriatric*[tiab] OR "older adult*" [tiab])</p> <p>AND</p> <p>("general population"[tiab] OR community[tiab] OR "healthy volunteer*" [tiab] OR "population-based"[tiab] OR "population based"[tiab] OR "nonclinical"[tiab] OR "non-clinical"[tiab] OR epidemiologic*[tiab] OR "household survey"[tiab] OR "Mental Disorders"[MeSH Terms] OR "mental health"[MeSH Terms] OR "mental disorder*" [tiab] OR "psychiatric"[tiab] OR psychosis[tiab] OR "psychological"[tiab] OR "mood disorder*" [tiab] OR "affective disorder*" [tiab] OR "Substance-Related Disorders"[MeSH Terms] OR "substance use"[tiab] OR "substance-use"[tiab] OR "drug use"[tiab] OR "drug-use"[tiab] OR "drug abuse"[tiab] OR "substance abuse"[tiab] OR "substance-abuse"[tiab] OR "alcohol use"[tiab]</p>	<p>Construct:</p> <p>("Sleep Initiation and Maintenance Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Sleep Initiation and Maintenance Disorders"[Majr] OR "Disorders of Initiating and Maintaining Sleep"[tiab] OR "DIMS (Disorders of Initiating and Maintaining Sleep)" [tiab:~0] OR "Early Awakening"[tiab] OR "Awakening, Early"[tiab] OR "Nonorganic Insomnia"[tiab] OR "Insomnia, Nonorganic"[tiab:~0] OR "Primary Insomnia"[tiab] OR "Insomnia, Primary"[tiab] OR "Transient Insomnia"[tiab] OR "Insomnia, Transient"[tiab] OR "Rebound Insomnia"[tiab] OR "Insomnia, Rebound"[tiab] OR "Secondary Insomnia"[tiab] OR "Insomnia, Secondary"[tiab] OR "Sleep Initiation Dysfunction"[tiab:~0] OR "Dysfunction, Sleep Initiation"[tiab:~0] OR "Dysfunctions, Sleep Initiation"[tiab:~0] OR "Sleep Initiation Dysfunctions"[tiab:~0] OR "Sleeplessness"[tiab] OR "Insomnia</p>		

	OR "alcohol-use"[tiab] OR "alcohol abuse"[tiab] OR "opioid use"[tiab] OR "cannabis use"[tiab] OR "stimulant use"[tiab] OR "mental health"[tiab] OR "SUD"[tiab]) AND (Humans[Mesh])	Disorder"[tiab] OR "Insomnia Disorders"[tiab] OR "Insomnia"[tiab] OR "Insomnias"[tiab] OR "Chronic Insomnia"[tiab] OR "Insomnia, Chronic"[tiab] OR "Psychophysiological Insomnia"[tiab] OR "Insomnia, Psychophysiological"[tiab] OR "Sleep"[tiab] OR "Sleep Condition"[tiab])		
Instrument	("WHODAS*"[tiab] OR "WHODAS 2.0"[tiab] OR "World Health Organization Disability Assessment Schedule"[tiab]) AND ("self-report"[tiab] OR "self-reported"[tiab] OR "self-administered"[tiab] OR "self administered"[tiab] OR "patient-reported"[tiab] OR "patient reported"[tiab] OR "adaptive testing"[tiab] OR "computer adaptive testing"[tiab] OR "Patient Reported Outcome Measures"[MeSH])	("Sleep Condition Indicator"[tiab] OR "the SCI"[tiab:-0] OR "Insomnia Screening"[tiab] OR "Sleep Assessment"[tiab])	(whodas [TI] OR "World Health Organization Disability Assessment Schedule" [TI] OR "who-das" [TI] OR "who das" [TI]) AND ("12" OR "twelve") AND (hasabstract[text])	(whodas OR whodas OR who/das OR "world health organization disability assessment schedule")
Measurement properties	((instrumentation[sh] OR "Validation Studies"[pt] OR "reproducibility of results"[MeSH Terms] OR reproducib*[tiab] OR "psychometrics"[MeSH] OR psychometr*[tiab] OR clinimetr*[tiab] OR clinometr*[tiab] OR "observer variation"[MeSH] OR "observer	(instrumentation[sh] OR methods[sh] OR "Validation Studies"[pt] OR "Comparative Study"[pt] OR "psychometrics"[MeSH] OR psychometr*[tiab] OR clinimetr*[tw] OR clinometr*[tw] OR "outcome assessment (health care)"[MeSH] OR "outcome		

	<p>variation"[tiab] OR "discriminant analysis"[MeSH] OR reliab*[tiab] OR valid*[tiab] OR coefficient[tiab] OR "internal consistency"[tiab] OR (cronbach*[tiab] AND (alpha[tiab] OR alphas[tiab])) OR "item correlation"[tiab] OR "item correlations"[tiab] OR "item selection"[tiab] OR "item selections"[tiab] OR "item reduction"[tiab] OR "item reductions"[tiab] OR agreement[tiab] OR precision[tiab] OR imprecision[tiab] OR "precise values"[tiab] OR test-retest[tiab] OR (test[tiab] AND retest[tiab]) OR (reliab*[tiab] AND (test[tiab] OR retest[tiab])) OR stability[tiab] OR interrater[tiab] OR inter-rater[tiab] OR intrarater[tiab] OR intra-rater[tiab] OR intertester[tiab] OR inter-tester[tiab] OR intratester[tiab] OR intra-tester[tiab] OR interobserver[tiab] OR inter-observer[tiab] OR intraobserver[tiab] OR intra-observer[tiab] OR intertechnician[tiab] OR inter-technician[tiab] OR intratechnician[tiab] OR intra-technician[tiab] OR interexaminer[tiab] OR inter-examiner[tiab] OR intraexaminer[tiab] OR intra-examiner[tiab] OR interassay[tiab] OR inter-assay[tiab] OR intraassay[tiab] OR intra-assay[tiab] OR interindividual[tiab] OR inter-individual[tiab] OR intraindividual[tiab] OR intra-individual[tiab] OR interparticipant[tiab]</p>	<p>assessment"[tiab] OR "outcome measure*" [tw] OR "observer variation"[MeSH] OR "observer variation"[tiab] OR "Health Status Indicators"[Mesh] OR "reproducibility of results"[MeSH] OR reproducib*[tiab] OR "discriminant analysis"[MeSH] OR reliab*[tiab] OR unreliab*[tiab] OR valid*[tiab] OR "coefficient of variation"[tiab] OR coefficient[tiab] OR homogeneity[tiab] OR homogeneous[tiab] OR "internal consistency"[tiab] OR (cronbach*[tiab] AND (alpha[tiab] OR alphas[tiab])) OR (item[tiab] AND (correlation*[tiab] OR selection*[tiab] OR reduction*[tiab])) OR agreement[tw] OR precision[tw] OR imprecision[tw] OR "precise values"[tw] OR test-retest[tiab] OR (test[tiab] AND retest[tiab]) OR (reliab*[tiab] AND (test[tiab] OR retest[tiab])) OR stability[tiab] OR interrater[tiab] OR inter-rater[tiab] OR intrarater[tiab] OR intra-rater[tiab] OR intertester[tiab] OR inter-tester[tiab] OR intratester[tiab] OR intra-tester[tiab] OR interobserver[tiab] OR inter-observer[tiab] OR intraobserver[tiab] OR intra-observer[tiab] OR intertechnician[tiab] OR</p>		
--	--	--	--	--

	<p>OR inter-participant[tiab] OR intraparticipant[tiab] OR intra-participant[tiab] OR kappa[tiab] OR kappa's[tiab] OR kappas[tiab] OR repeatab*[tiab] OR ((replicab*[tiab] OR repeated[tiab]) AND (measure[tiab] OR measures[tiab] OR findings[tiab] OR result[tiab] OR results[tiab] OR test[tiab] OR tests[tiab])) OR generaliza*[tiab] OR generalisa*[tiab] OR concordance[tiab] OR (intraclass[tiab] AND correlation*[tiab]) OR discriminative[tiab] OR "known group"[tiab] OR "factor analysis"[tiab] OR "factor analyses"[tiab] OR dimensionality[tiab] OR subscale*[tiab] OR "multitrait scaling analysis"[tiab] OR "multitrait scaling analyses"[tiab] OR "item discriminant"[tiab] OR "interscale correlation"[tiab] OR "interscale correlations"[tiab] OR ((error[tiab] OR errors[tiab]) AND (measure*[tiab] OR correlat*[tiab] OR evaluat*[tiab] OR accuracy[tiab] OR accurate[tiab] OR precision[tiab] OR mean[tiab])) OR "individual variability"[tiab] OR "variability analysis"[tiab] OR (uncertainty[tiab] AND (measurement[tiab] OR measuring[tiab])) OR "standard error of measurement"[tiab] OR sensitiv*[tiab] OR responsive*[tiab] OR (small*[tiab] AND</p>	<p>inter-technician[tiab] OR intratechnician[tiab] OR intra-technician[tiab] OR interexaminer[tiab] OR inter-examiner[tiab] OR intraexaminer[tiab] OR intra-examiner[tiab] OR interassay[tiab] OR inter-assay[tiab] OR intraassay[tiab] OR intra-assay[tiab] OR interindividual[tiab] OR inter-individual[tiab] OR intraindividual[tiab] OR intra-individual[tiab] OR interparticipant[tiab] OR inter-participant[tiab] OR intraparticipant[tiab] OR intra-participant[tiab] OR kappa[tiab] OR kappa's[tiab] OR kappas[tiab] OR repeatab*[tw] OR ((replicab*[tw] OR repeated[tw]) AND (measure[tw] OR measures[tw] OR findings[tw] OR result[tw] OR results[tw] OR test[tw] OR tests[tw])) OR generaliza*[tiab] OR generalisa*[tiab] OR concordance[tiab] OR (intraclass[tiab] AND correlation*[tiab]) OR discriminative[tiab] OR "known group"[tiab] OR "factor analysis"[tiab] OR "factor analyses"[tiab] OR "factor structure"[tiab] OR "factor structures"[tiab] OR dimension*[tiab] OR subscale*[tiab] OR (multitrait[tiab] AND scaling[tiab] AND (analysis[tiab] OR analyses[tiab])) OR "item</p>		
--	--	---	--	--

	<p>(real[tiab] OR detectable[tiab]) AND (change[tiab] OR difference[tiab])) OR "meaningful change"[tiab] OR "minimal important change"[tiab] OR "minimal important difference"[tiab] OR "minimally important change"[tiab] OR "minimally important difference"[tiab] OR "minimal detectable change"[tiab] OR "minimal detectable difference"[tiab] OR "minimally detectable change"[tiab] OR "minimally detectable difference"[tiab] OR "minimal real change"[tiab] OR "minimal real difference"[tiab] OR "minimally real change"[tiab] OR "minimally real difference"[tiab] OR "ceiling effect"[tiab] OR "floor effect"[tiab] OR "item response model"[tiab] OR irt[tiab] OR rasch[tiab] OR "differential item functioning"[tiab] OR dif[tiab] OR "computer adaptive testing"[tiab] OR "item bank"[tiab] OR "cross-cultural equivalence"[tiab])</p>	<p>discriminant"[tiab] OR "interscale correlation*" [tiab] OR error[tiab] OR errors[tiab] OR "individual variability"[tiab] OR "interval variability"[tiab] OR "rate variability"[tiab] OR (variability[tiab] AND (analysis[tiab] OR values[tiab])) OR (uncertainty[tiab] AND (measurement[tiab] OR measuring[tiab])) OR "standard error of measurement"[tiab] OR sensitiv*[tiab] OR responsive*[tiab] OR (limit[tiab] AND detection[tiab]) OR "minimal detectable concentration"[tiab] OR interpretab*[tiab] OR ((minimal[tiab] OR minimally[tiab] OR clinical[tiab] OR clinically[tiab]) AND (important[tiab] OR significant[tiab] OR detectable[tiab]) AND (change[tiab] OR difference[tiab])) OR (small*[tiab] AND (real[tiab] OR detectable[tiab]) AND (change[tiab] OR difference[tiab])) OR "meaningful change"[tiab] OR "ceiling effect"[tiab] OR "floor effect"[tiab] OR "Item response model"[tiab] OR IRT[tiab] OR Rasch[tiab] OR "Differential item functioning"[tiab] OR DIF[tiab] OR "computer adaptive testing"[tiab] OR "item bank"[tiab] OR "cross-cultural equivalence"[tiab])</p>		
--	--	--	--	--

		Articles retrieved: 899 Articles included: 19	Articles retrieved: 191 Articles included: 14	Articles retrieved: 5819 Articles included: 810
--	--	--	--	--

Tables B, C, and D present the results of our preliminary searches using variations of the initial search strategy, developed based on comparisons with search strategies employed in previous systematic reviews.

Table B. Search strategy used for systematic search on PubMed database (updated on 03 December 2025).

Block	Search strategy	Number of retrieved items
Population (#1)	("adult"[MeSH Terms] OR adult*[tiab] OR "adolescent"[MeSH Terms] OR adolescen*[tiab] OR teen*[tiab] OR youth*[tiab] OR "young people"[tiab] OR elderly[tiab] OR geriatric*[tiab] OR "older adult*" [tiab]) AND ("general population"[tiab] OR community[tiab] OR "healthy volunteer*" [tiab] OR "population-based"[tiab] OR "population based"[tiab] OR "nonclinical"[tiab] OR "non-clinical"[tiab] OR epidemiologic*[tiab] OR "household survey"[tiab]) OR ("Mental Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Psychopathology"[Mesh] OR "Mental Health"[Mesh] OR "Affective Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Mood Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Anxiety Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Personality Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Neurodevelopmental Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Somatoform Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Psychotic Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Schizophrenia Spectrum and Other Psychotic Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Stress Disorders, Post-Traumatic"[Mesh] OR "Trauma and Stressor Related Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Obsessive-	2,341,131

	<p>Compulsive Disorder"[Mesh] OR "Compulsive Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Attention Deficit and Disruptive Behavior Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Autistic Disorder"[Mesh] OR "Autism Spectrum Disorder"[Mesh] OR psychopathology[tiab] OR "mental disorder*"[tiab] OR "mental illness*"[tiab] OR "psychiatric disorder*"[tiab] OR "psychological disorder*"[tiab] OR "anxiety disorder*"[tiab] OR "mood disorder*"[tiab] OR depression[tiab] OR depressive[tiab] OR "bipolar disorder*"[tiab] OR "psychotic disorder*"[tiab] OR psychosis[tiab] OR "personality disorder*"[tiab] OR "attention deficit*"[tiab] OR ADHD[tiab] OR autism[tiab] OR autistic[tiab]) OR ("Substance-Related Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Substance Abuse, Intravenous"[Mesh] OR "Alcohol-Related Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Alcoholism"[Mesh] OR "Opioid-Related Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Cocaine-Related Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Amphetamine-Related Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Cannabis-Related Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Tobacco Use Disorder"[Mesh] OR "substance use disorder*"[tiab] OR "substance-related disorder*"[tiab] OR "drug use disorder*"[tiab] OR "drug abuse"[tiab] OR "drug dependence"[tiab] OR "alcohol use disorder*"[tiab] OR alcoholism[tiab] OR "opioid use disorder*"[tiab] OR "cannabis use disorder*"[tiab] OR "stimulant use disorder*"[tiab] OR "tobacco use disorder*"[tiab] OR "nicotine dependence"[tiab])</p> <p>AND (Humans[Mesh])</p>	
Instrument (#2)	<p>("WHODAS*"[tiab] OR "WHODAS 2.0"[tiab] OR "World Health Organization Disability Assessment Schedule"[tiab] OR "who-das*"[tiab] OR "who das*"[tiab] OR "who/das*"[tiab] OR "Disability Evaluation"[MeSH] OR "Disability Evaluation"[tiab])</p> <p>AND</p> <p>("self-report"[tiab] OR "self-reported"[tiab] OR "self-administered"[tiab] OR "self administered"[tiab] OR "patient-reported"[tiab] OR "patient reported"[tiab] OR "adaptive testing"[tiab] OR "computer adaptive</p>	5,996

	testing"[tiab] OR "Patient Reported Outcome Measures"[MeSH] OR proxy*[tiab] OR interviewer*[tiab])	
Measurement properties (#3)	((instrumentation[sh] OR "Validation Studies"[pt] OR "reproducibility of results"[MeSH Terms] OR reproducib*[tiab] OR "psychometrics"[MeSH] OR psychometr*[tiab] OR clinimetr*[tiab] OR clinometr*[tiab] OR "observer variation"[MeSH] OR "observer variation"[tiab] OR "discriminant analysis"[MeSH] OR reliab*[tiab] OR valid*[tiab] OR coefficient[tiab] OR "internal consistency"[tiab] OR (cronbach*[tiab] AND (alpha[tiab] OR alphas[tiab])) OR "item correlation"[tiab] OR "item correlations"[tiab] OR "item selection"[tiab] OR "item selections"[tiab] OR "item reduction"[tiab] OR "item reductions"[tiab] OR agreement[tiab] OR precision[tiab] OR imprecision[tiab] OR "precise values"[tiab] OR test-retest[tiab] OR (test[tiab] AND retest[tiab]) OR (reliab*[tiab] AND (test[tiab] OR retest[tiab]))) OR stability[tiab] OR interrater[tiab] OR inter-rater[tiab] OR intrarater[tiab] OR intrarater[tiab] OR intertester[tiab] OR inter-tester[tiab] OR intratester[tiab] OR intra-tester[tiab] OR interobserver[tiab] OR inter-observer[tiab] OR intraobserver[tiab] OR intra-observer[tiab] OR intertechnician[tiab] OR inter-technician[tiab] OR intratechnician[tiab] OR intra-technician[tiab] OR interexaminer[tiab] OR inter-examiner[tiab] OR intraexaminer[tiab] OR intra-examiner[tiab] OR interassay[tiab] OR inter-assay[tiab] OR intraassay[tiab] OR intra-assay[tiab] OR interindividual[tiab] OR inter-individual[tiab] OR intraindividual[tiab] OR intra-individual[tiab] OR interparticipant[tiab] OR inter-participant[tiab] OR intraparticipant[tiab] OR intra-participant[tiab] OR kappa[tiab] OR kappa's[tiab] OR kappas[tiab] OR repeatab*[tiab] OR ((replicab*[tiab] OR repeated[tiab]) AND (measure[tiab] OR measures[tiab] OR findings[tiab] OR result[tiab] OR results[tiab] OR test[tiab] OR tests[tiab])) OR generaliza*[tiab] OR generalisa*[tiab] OR concordance[tiab] OR (intraclass[tiab] AND correlation*[tiab]) OR discriminative[tiab] OR "known group"[tiab] OR "factor analysis"[tiab] OR "factor analyses"[tiab] OR dimensionality[tiab] OR subscale*[tiab] OR "multitrait scaling analysis"[tiab] OR "multitrait scaling	6,449,230

	<p>analyses"[tiab] OR "item discriminant"[tiab]OR "interscale correlation"[tiab] OR "interscale correlations"[tiab] OR ((error[tiab] OR errors[tiab]) AND (measure*[tiab] OR correlat*[tiab] OR evaluat*[tiab] OR accuracy[tiab] OR accurate[tiab] OR precision[tiab] OR mean[tiab])) OR "individual variability"[tiab] OR "variability analysis"[tiab] OR (uncertainty[tiab] AND (measurement[tiab] OR measuring[tiab])) OR "standard error of measurement"[tiab] OR sensitiv*[tiab] OR responsive*[tiab] OR (small*[tiab] AND (real[tiab] OR detectable[tiab]) AND (change[tiab] OR difference[tiab])) OR "meaningful change"[tiab] OR "minimal important change"[tiab] OR "minimal important difference"[tiab] OR "minimally important change"[tiab] OR "minimally important difference"[tiab] OR "minimal detectable change"[tiab] OR "minimal detectable difference"[tiab] OR "minimally detectable change"[tiab] OR "minimally detectable difference"[tiab] OR "minimal real change"[tiab] OR "minimal real difference"[tiab] OR "minimally real change"[tiab] OR "minimally real difference"[tiab] OR "ceiling effect"[tiab] OR "floor effect"[tiab] OR "item response model"[tiab] OR irt[tiab] OR rasch[tiab] OR "differential item functioning"[tiab] OR dif[tiab] OR "computer adaptive testing"[tiab] OR "item bank"[tiab] OR "cross-cultural equivalence"[tiab])</p>	
All	#1 AND #2 AND #3	844

Table C. Search strategy used for systematic search (No COSMIN properties filter) on PubMed database (updated on 03 December 2025).

Block	Search strategy	Number of retrieved items
Population (#1)	<p>("adult"[MeSH Terms] OR adult*[tiab] OR "adolescent"[MeSH Terms] OR adolescen*[tiab] OR teen*[tiab] OR youth*[tiab] OR "young people"[tiab] OR elderly[tiab] OR geriatric*[tiab] OR "older adult*"[tiab])</p> <p>AND</p> <p>("general population"[tiab] OR community[tiab] OR "healthy volunteer*"[tiab] OR "population-based"[tiab] OR "population based"[tiab] OR "nonclinical"[tiab] OR "non-clinical"[tiab] OR epidemiologic*[tiab] OR "household survey"[tiab]) OR ("Mental Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Psychopathology"[Mesh] OR "Mental Health"[Mesh] OR "Affective Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Mood Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Anxiety Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Personality Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Neurodevelopmental Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Somatoform Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Psychotic Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Schizophrenia Spectrum and Other Psychotic Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Stress Disorders, Post-Traumatic"[Mesh] OR "Trauma and Stressor Related Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder"[Mesh] OR "Compulsive Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Attention Deficit and Disruptive Behavior Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Autistic Disorder"[Mesh] OR "Autism Spectrum Disorder"[Mesh] OR psychopathology[tiab] OR "mental disorder*"[tiab] OR "mental illness*"[tiab] OR "psychiatric disorder*"[tiab] OR "psychological disorder*"[tiab] OR "anxiety disorder*"[tiab] OR "mood disorder*"[tiab] OR depression[tiab] OR depressive[tiab] OR "bipolar disorder*"[tiab] OR "psychotic disorder*"[tiab] OR psychosis[tiab] OR "personality disorder*"[tiab] OR "attention deficit*"[tiab] OR</p>	2,341,131

	<p>ADHD[tiab] OR autism[tiab] OR autistic[tiab]) OR ("Substance-Related Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Substance Abuse, Intravenous"[Mesh] OR "Alcohol-Related Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Alcoholism"[Mesh] OR "Opioid-Related Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Cocaine-Related Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Amphetamine-Related Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Cannabis-Related Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Tobacco Use Disorder"[Mesh] OR "substance use disorder*"[tiab] OR "substance-related disorder*"[tiab] OR "drug use disorder*"[tiab] OR "drug abuse"[tiab] OR "drug dependence"[tiab] OR "alcohol use disorder*"[tiab] OR alcoholism[tiab] OR "opioid use disorder*"[tiab] OR "cannabis use disorder*"[tiab] OR "stimulant use disorder*"[tiab] OR "tobacco use disorder*"[tiab] OR "nicotine dependence"[tiab])</p> <p>AND (Humans[Mesh])</p>	
Instrument (#2)	<p>("WHODAS*"[tiab] OR "WHODAS 2.0"[tiab] OR "World Health Organization Disability Assessment Schedule"[tiab] OR "who-das*"[tiab] OR "who das*"[tiab] OR "who/das*"[tiab] OR "Disability Evaluation"[MeSH] OR "Disability Evaluation"[tiab])</p> <p>AND</p> <p>("self-report"[tiab] OR "self-reported"[tiab] OR "self-administered"[tiab] OR "self administered"[tiab] OR "patient-reported"[tiab] OR "patient reported"[tiab] OR "adaptive testing"[tiab] OR "computer adaptive testing"[tiab] OR "Patient Reported Outcome Measures"[MeSH] OR proxy*[tiab] OR interviewer*[tiab])</p>	5,996
All	#1 AND #2	1,897

Table D. Search strategy used for systematic search on PubMed database including only WHODAS-related terms (updated on 03 December 2025)

Block	Search strategy	Number of retrieved items
Instrument	("WHODAS*" [tiab] OR "WHODAS 2.0" [tiab] OR "World Health Organization Disability Assessment Schedule" [tiab] OR "who-das*" [tiab] OR "who das*" [tiab] OR "who/das*" [tiab] OR "World Health Organization Disability Assessment" [tiab] OR "WHO Disability Assessment" [tiab])	1,649

Screening process

In total, 200 records were screened at the title and abstract level, of which 14 studies progressed to full-text review. The screening process is summarized in a PRISMA flow diagram (**Figure 1**). Inclusion and exclusion criteria applied at both the title/abstract and full-text screening stages of the pilot study were as follows:

Inclusion criteria

- Empirical studies examining at least one measurement property of the WHODAS 2.0.
- Studies conducted in the general population or in individuals with mental health or substance use disorders.
- Studies employing any design.
- Studies conducted in any setting or country.

Exclusion criteria

- Non-peer-reviewed publications (e.g., dissertations, conference abstracts).
- Studies that did not evaluate any measurement properties.
- Studies assessing versions of the WHODAS 2.0 other than the 12-item.
- Studies that used the WHODAS 2.0 solely as a comparator instrument for validating other instruments.

Systematic reviews were not included in the present study; however, they were tagged to provide an overview of the existing literature and to identify additional relevant primary studies that may not have been captured by the search strategy. Studies assessing the measurement properties of the 12+24-item and the 36-item versions of the WHODAS 2.0 were also tagged.

Figure 1. PRISMA flowchart summarizing the screening process of the WHODAS 2.0 pilot study.

Data extraction

Data extraction was completed for 18 studies. This included 6 studies deemed eligible following full-text assessment of the 200 records screened in the pilot feasibility study, as well as an additional 12 eligible studies identified after full-text assessment of a random sample drawn from the 1,649 records retrieved by the search strategy.

The extracted data covered the following domains:

- Study characteristics
- WHODAS 2.0 version and intended purpose
- Administration format
- Sample size and participant demographics
- Country of study
- Measurement properties assessed (classified using the COSMIN taxonomy, along with other properties: feasibility, and interpretability)

The extraction table is provided in a Supplementary File, accessible [here](#).

Tables presented below (Tables E and F) provide an executive summary of the data extracted as part of the pilot study.

Table E. Summary of the revised studies.

Study	Population	N	COSMIN properties examined	N. of COSMIN properties	Other properties
Abdin, et al. (2025)	Adults with depression or anxiety	308	Responsiveness	1/9	Interpretability
Abdin, et al (2023)	Adults with schizophrenia, depression, anxiety, and diabetes	1076	Structural validity, internal consistency, cross-cultural validity/measurement invariance, reliability, construct validity	5/9	Interpretability
Amoretti S et al. (2025)	Adults with ADHD	557	Structural validity, internal consistency, convergent validity	3/9	--
Ämmälä AJ et al. (2025)	Adults with depression	4,945	Responsiveness	1/9	--
Cavero V et al. (2025)	Community mental health stakeholders	78	--	0/9	Feasibility

Cheng S et al. (2025)	Older adults	2170	Construct validity, criterion validity	2/9	--
Ferro et al (2023)	Adolescents, mental disorders, households	1968	Structural validity, cross-cultural validity/ measurement invariance	2/9	--
Habtamu et al. (2018)	Adults, mental disorders	324	Construct validity	1/9	--
Holmberg et al. (2021)	Adults, psychotic disorders	881	Structural validity, internal consistency, construct validity	3/9	--
Kimber et al. (2015)	Youth, adults, households	25063	Structural validity	1/9	--
McDonald et al. (2023)	Adolescents, mental disorders	56	Internal consistency, measurement error, construct validity	3/9	--
Mihretu A et al. (2025)	Adults with depression, anxiety and psychosis	2,834	Structural validity, internal consistency, construct validity, responsiveness	4/9	--
Risal, et al. (2021)	Adults with any current psychiatric disorder	149	Content validity, internal consistency, reliability, criterion validity, construct validity	5/9	--
Theotokatos, et al. (2023)	Adults with disabilities	10163	Structural validity, internal consistency, construct validity	3/9	--
Tompke et al. (2020)	Adolescents, healthy, mental and physical disorders	1851	Structural validity, internal consistency, cross-cultural validity/ measurement invariance	3/9	--

Wada et al. (2021)	Patients with schizophrenia	350	Structural validity, internal consistency, reliability, construct validity	4/9	--
Weeks et al. (2016)	Adults, military	6700	Structural validity, internal consistency	2/9	--
Zhou et al. (2020)	Adults, mental disorders	410	Structural validity, cross-cultural validity/ measurement invariance, reliability	3/9	--

Table F. Aggregated summary of the revised studies.

Domain	Summary from pilot extraction
Number of studies	18
Publication year(s)	2015-2025
WHODAS 2.0 version	12-items, interviewer and self-administered
Population type	Clinical populations with mental disorders, as well as general adult and adolescent populations, and a few specific groups such as adults with disabilities, military personnel.
Geographical setting	Brazil, Canada (5), China (2), Ethiopia (2), Finland, Ghana, Greece, India, Japan, Nepal, Nigeria, Peru (2), Singapore (2), South Africa, Spain, Sweden
Most frequently assessed COSMIN property	Structural validity (11), internal consistency (10), construct validity (7)
Less frequently assessed COSMIN property	Convergent validity (1), measurement error (1), content validity (1)
Other properties	Interpretability (2)

Insights from the pilot review and implications for inclusion criteria and search strategy

The pilot review demonstrated that, despite broad search terms, the overall number of eligible studies was relatively modest and that WHODAS 2.0 has been applied across heterogeneous populations and contexts. To maximize the available evidence base and ensure a comprehensive evaluation of its measurement properties, the inclusion criteria were therefore expanded to include all populations, rather than limiting eligibility to specific clinical groups. Concurrently, the search strategy was refined to improve retrieval of studies on measurement properties addressing both commonly assessed and underrepresented measurement properties. While retaining the COSMIN measurement property filter as its foundation, additional keywords were incorporated to capture interpretability, feasibility, diagnostic or screening accuracy, content validity, cross-cultural validity, measurement invariance, and structural validity. These refinements aim to ensure a more comprehensive coverage of the evidence in the full review.

Appendix B. Operationalization of the measurement properties across the project

The table below provides operational definitions of each measurement property considered for this systematic review, together with practical guidance for reviewers on how to identify relevant evidence in primary studies. For each property, we specify its conceptual definition and indicate the types of analyses, statistics, or study features that reviewers should look for (but not limited to) when extracting and classifying the evidence on measurement properties. We also included additional characteristics of the WHODAS 2.0 that, while not considered measurement properties, constitute important properties when using a measurement tool (i.e., feasibility, interpretability, acceptability). The definitions of these other properties are theoretical and do not account for the context of use, such as the population or the intended purpose of the instrument application. Additionally, we recognize that measurement properties are the product of an interaction between a measurement tool and the population in which it is used, and therefore may vary across different populations. For instance, convergent validity may hold in a sample of individuals with diagnosed depression but not in a sample without mental health disorders.

The definitions and operationalizations are based on the COSMIN guidelines (Mokkink et al., 2024), which is the most comprehensive framework we identified. However, we acknowledge that measurement science is an evolving field, and that alternative definitions, methods, and future advancements may further refine how measurement properties are conceptualized, assessed, and interpreted.

Measurement (and other related) properties	Definitions and Operationalization
1. Content validity	<p>Definition: Content validity is the degree to which the content of an instrument adequately reflects the construct to be measured. It comprises three aspects: relevance (whether items are pertinent to the construct and population), comprehensiveness (whether all key aspects of the construct are covered), and comprehensibility (whether items, instructions, response options, and recall period are understood as intended).</p> <p>Typical indicators: Content validity evidence may come from concept elicitation studies (e.g., qualitative interviews or focus groups) assessing whether all key concepts are represented; from pilot or cognitive interviewing studies assessing</p>

	comprehensibility of items, instructions, response options, and recall period; or from separate content validity studies in which people with lived experiences or professionals judge relevance, comprehensiveness, and comprehensibility. Analyses may include e.g., content analysis, framework analysis, deductive analysis, or grounded theory.
2. Structural validity	<p>Definition: Structural validity refers to the degree to which the scores of a PROM adequately reflect the dimensionality of the construct to be measured, that is, whether the items group into the expected factor structure or latent model.</p> <p>Typical indicators: Structural validity is commonly evaluated during the development of the measures using principal component analysis (PCA) or exploratory factor analysis (EFA). Structural validity is further confirmed with confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). Reported results may include the number of factors, item–factor loadings, explained variance, eigenvalues, model fit indices (e.g., CFI, TLI, RMSEA, SRMR), and tests of model assumptions such as unidimensionality, local independence, monotonicity, or item fit statistics. Item response theory (IRT) or Rasch models can also be used to examine the items in a scale.</p>
3. Internal consistency	<p>Definition: Internal consistency refers to the degree of interrelatedness among items in a scale. It reflects whether items consistently measure the same underlying construct, assuming unidimensionality.</p> <p>Typical indicators: Internal consistency is typically quantified using Cronbach’s alpha, McDonald’s Omega, or IRT/Rasch-based reliability indices (e.g., standard error of theta). Interpretation of these statistics requires evidence that the items form a unidimensional scale, which should be established through prior assessment of structural validity.</p>
4. Cross-cultural validity and measurement invariance	<p>Definition: Cross-cultural validity (or measurement invariance) refers to the extent to which PROM items perform equivalently across different groups, such as languages, cultures, genders, age groups, or clinical populations. It assesses whether individuals with the same underlying level of the construct respond similarly to the items, regardless of group membership.</p>

	<p>Typical indicators: Cross-cultural validity is commonly evaluated using multi-group factor analysis, including tests of configural, metric, and scalar invariance, or through differential item functioning (DIF) analyses. Studies may also examine longitudinal measurement invariance to assess score comparability over time. Comparisons typically involve culturally or linguistically distinct groups, and may also include other relevant subgroups (e.g., gender, ages, etc.).</p>
5. Reliability	<p>Definition: Reliability refers to the proportion of total variance in scores that is due to true differences between individuals. It reflects the ability of an instrument to distinguish between respondents.</p> <p>Typical indicators: Reliability is evaluated using repeated measurements in participants who are expected/assumed to remain stable on the construct. Measurements should be conducted under identical conditions, including the same PROM version, administration mode, response format, and setting, except for the specific source of variation being examined. Most commonly, reliability is assessed over time (test–retest reliability), but studies may also examine consistency across administration modes (e.g., paper vs digital), response formats (e.g., Likert vs VAS), or administrators (e.g., self-report vs interviewer-assisted/read aloud). Reported statistics typically include intraclass correlation coefficients (ICC) or kappa values, with specification of the ICC model when applicable. Some studies report Pearson or Spearman correlations, although these are less appropriate for assessing reliability.</p>
6. Measurement error	<p>Definition: Measurement error refers to the systematic and random error in a PROM score that is not attributable to true change in the construct being measured. It refers to the precision of the score. Measurement error is sometimes referred to as agreement and is evaluated using repeated measurements in participants who are assumed to be stable on the construct. The same data collected for the assessment of reliability can be used to evaluate measurement error.</p> <p>Typical indicators: Measurement error is assessed using repeated measurements in stable participants, often drawing on the same study designs used for reliability analyses. Reported statistics may include the standard error of measurement (SEM), smallest detectable change (SDC), limits of agreement (LoA), or percentage agreement for categorical scores. These indices quantify the amount of error around an observed score or change score. Kappa statistics are not measures of measurement error but of reliability.</p>

7. Criterion validity	<p>Definition: Criterion validity refers to the degree to which PROM scores are an adequate reflection of a reference standard (gold standard).</p> <p>Definition by the review team:</p> <p>Given that the WHODAS 2.0 is a generic measure of functioning and disability grounded in the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF), appropriate external criteria include well-established and widely accepted measures of disability or functioning. Examples reported in the literature include other validated disability instruments (e.g., SF-36, Social and Occupational Functioning Scale, Sheehan Disability Scale), and clinician-rated global functioning or severity classifications (e.g., Global Assessment of Functioning, New York Heart Association functional class).</p> <p>Therefore, upon discussion within the review team, we agreed that the selected criterion should be specific to the construct of functioning or disability and appropriate for the target population. For example, in adults with chronic musculoskeletal conditions, the SF-36 (particularly its Physical Functioning and Role Physical subscales) may serve as an appropriate external criterion for assessing the criterion validity of the WHODAS 2.0, as both instruments capture limitations in daily activities and participation. Symptom-based measures or diagnostic classifications are not considered suitable gold standards for criterion validity of the WHODAS 2.0, as they assess different constructs and do not directly quantify functional limitations or participation restrictions.</p> <p>The ability of the WHODAS 2.0 scores to discriminate between diagnostic or severity groups will be examined under hypothesis testing for construct validity or diagnostic accuracy.</p>
8. Diagnostic accuracy	<p><u>Definition by the review team</u></p> <p>For the WHODAS 2.0, the review team will consider classification accuracy for identifying individuals with clinically relevant levels of disability or functional impairment, rather than the presence or absence of a specific diagnosis. Diagnostic and screening accuracy are defined as the ability of an instrument to correctly classify study participants into predefined categories based on an external criterion (reference standard) (Deeks & Bossuyt,</p>

	<p>2023/2023).</p> <p>For diagnostic accuracy, the WHODAS 2.0 may be evaluated for its ability to classify individuals as having clinically significant disability in clinical populations. For screening accuracy, the WHODAS 2.0 may be evaluated for its ability to identify previously unrecognised disability or functional impairment in non-clinical or community populations</p> <p><u>Typical indicators</u></p> <p>We will include studies examining the accuracy of the WHODAS 2.0 against a binary or categorical external criterion of disability or functioning, defined using clinician-rated assessments, structured functional evaluations, administrative classifications, or other established thresholds of disability status. Diagnostic classifications alone will not be considered appropriate reference standards.</p> <p>Typical indicators of diagnostic or screening accuracy include sensitivity, specificity, positive and negative predictive values, likelihood ratios, diagnostic odds ratios, area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC), and 2×2 classification tables. Studies may assess one or multiple WHODAS 2.0 cut-off values to examine classification performance across thresholds, commonly using ROC analyses.</p>
<p>9. Hypothesis testing for construct validity</p>	<p>Definition:</p> <p>Hypothesis testing for construct validity evaluates whether PROM scores behave as expected in relation to other measures or groups, based on a priori hypotheses defined by the review team.</p> <p>Hypotheses formulated by the review team:</p> <p>The WHODAS 2.0 is a generic measure of functioning and disability designed to assess limitations across six life domains and participation in daily life. Accordingly, we conceptualized construct validity based on its intended purposes: 1) measuring the level of disability in individuals, and 2) discriminating between groups with expected differences in functioning (e.g., clinical vs. non-clinical populations, mild vs. severe conditions).</p> <p><u>Using the WHODAS 2.0 as a measuring of functioning and disability</u></p>

	<p>In phase A (living mapping of the evidence base) We will first map studies reporting on construct validity to provide an overview of the comparator instruments used. We expect that for convergent validity, common comparators will include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Other PROMs assessing disability or functioning, such as SF-36 (Physical Functioning, Role Physical, Role Emotional, Social Functioning subscales), Sheehan Disability Scale (SDS), and other condition-specific disability scales (e.g., Neck Disability Index, Oswestry Disability Index). ● Clinician-reported functional assessments (ClinROMs) such as the Global Assessment of Functioning (GAF) or structured functional evaluations. <p>In phase B (evidence synthesis), further hypotheses for testing construct validity will be specified based on the comparators identified in Phase A. We will consider conducting evidence synthesis on convergent, divergent, and discriminant validity, depending on the needs of the research community and the available data. Decisions on synthesis and interpretation will be made in consultation with lived experience team members and clinicians. The usual indicators reported in included studies will include correlation coefficients between the WHODAS 2.0 total or domain scores and the comparator measures, as well as group differences across populations with expected variations in functioning.</p>
10. Responsiveness	<p>Definition: Responsiveness refers to the ability of a PROM to detect change over time in the construct to be measured. It concerns the accuracy of a change score in relation to a change in the construct measured.</p> <p>Typical indicators: Responsiveness is evaluated by testing <i>a priori</i> hypotheses about expected patterns of change, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Associations between change scores on the PROM and change scores on comparator instruments measuring the same or related constructs. ● Differences in change between groups expected to differ over time (e.g., intervention vs control groups, responders vs non-responders).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expected effect sizes following interventions with known or established effects. <p>Hypotheses should specify the expected direction and, where possible, the expected magnitude of change or association. Reported results may include correlations between change scores, mean differences in change, or effect sizes. Statistical significance alone is not sufficient; emphasis is placed on whether observed changes align with predefined hypotheses. Measures such as Guyatt’s responsiveness ratio or MIC/MID are not used to evaluate responsiveness itself, these are measures of interpretability.</p> <p>Hypotheses formulated by the review team:</p> <p>WHODAS 2.0</p> <p>Hypotheses are based on the expected direction and magnitude of change in WHODAS 2.0 scores relative to comparator measures. We expect moderate-to-strong correlations between change scores on the WHODAS 2.0 and change scores on established measures of disability, functioning. We expect that the comparator instruments most commonly found will be the same as those for construct validity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other PROMs of disability/functioning: SF-36, Sheehan Disability Scale, condition-specific disability scales (e.g., Neck Disability Index, Oswestry Disability Index) • Clinician-reported functional assessments: e.g., Global Assessment of Functioning (GAF), structured functional evaluations <p>During phase A (living mapping of the evidence base), we will first map studies reporting on responsiveness to provide an overview of the comparator instruments used.</p> <p>Definitive hypotheses for responsiveness will be specified after the mapping step based on the available comparators. As for Hypothesis testing for construct validity, we will synthesise evidence for responsiveness (Phase B) for the most used comparators, based on the needs of the research community and upon discussion with the members of the COLIVE-MH team.</p>
11. Feasibility	<p>Definition: Feasibility refers to the ease of administering the PROM in its intended context, considering practical constraints</p>

	<p>such as time, burden, cost, and accessibility.</p> <p>Typical indicators: Evidence on feasibility may be reported in studies describing the practical use of the PROM, including information on completion time, number of items, mode of administration, availability of translations, licensing or permission requirements, and implementation-related constraints. Some studies may also report indicators of acceptability or uptake.</p>
12. Interpretability	<p>Definition: Interpretability refers to the degree to which meaningful qualitative information can be assigned to PROM scores or change scores. Interpretability does not evaluate measurement quality itself but provides context for understanding what specific scores or changes represent.</p> <p>Typical indicators: Studies may report the distribution of scores, including floor and ceiling effects, reference values, or cut-off scores indicating severity levels (e.g., mild, moderate, severe). For change scores, studies may report minimal important change (MIC) or minimal important difference (MID), representing the smallest within-person change considered important. Although MIC/MID values are primarily used to interpret change, they are also necessary when evaluating measurement error.</p>
13. Acceptability	<p>Definition: How respondents perceive the experience of completing the scale, e.g., perceived intrusiveness, burden, potential harms or benefits.</p> <p>Typical indicators: Time of completion, number of missing responses, satisfaction with the questionnaire, qualitative reports on the experience of using the scale in research or clinical settings, etc.</p>

Appendix C. Search strategy

BLOCK 1: Instruments filter – including the full name and acronyms of the instrument but not the number of items.

("WHODAS*" [tiab] OR "WHO-DAS*" [tiab] OR "DASWHO*" [tiab] OR "DAS-WHO*" [tiab] OR "Disability Assessment Schedule*" [tiab] OR "WHO Disability Assessment*" [tiab] OR "World Health Organization Disability Assessment*" [tiab] OR "World Health Organization DAS*" [tiab])

BLOCK 2: COSMIN filter on measurement properties

AND ("instrumentation" [sh] OR "methods" [sh] OR "Validation Study" [pt] OR "Comparative Study" [pt] OR "psychometrics" [MeSH] OR "psychometr*" [tiab] OR "clinimetr*" [tw] OR "clinometr*" [tw] OR "Outcome Assessment, Health Care" [Mesh] OR "outcome assessment" [tiab] OR "outcome measure*" [tw] OR "observer variation" [MeSH] OR "observer variation" [tiab] OR "Health Status Indicators" [Mesh] OR "reproducibility of results" [MeSH] OR "reproducib*" [tiab] OR "discriminant analysis" [MeSH] OR "reliab*" [tiab] OR "unreliab*" [tiab] OR "valid*" [tiab] OR "coefficient of variation" [tiab] OR "coefficient" [tiab] OR "homogeneity" [tiab] OR "homogeneous" [tiab] OR "internal consistency" [tiab] OR ("cronbach*" [tiab] AND ("alpha" [tiab] OR "alphas" [tiab])) OR ("item" [tiab] AND ("correlation*" [tiab] OR "selection*" [tiab] OR "reduction*" [tiab])) OR "agreement" [tw] OR "precision" [tw] OR "imprecision" [tw] OR "precise values" [tw] OR "test-retest" [tiab] OR ("test" [tiab] AND "retest" [tiab]) OR ("reliab*" [tiab] AND ("test" [tiab] OR "retest" [tiab])) OR "stability" [tiab] OR "interrater" [tiab] OR "inter-rater" [tiab] OR "intrarater" [tiab] OR "intra-rater" [tiab] OR "intertester" [tiab] OR "inter-tester" [tiab] OR "intratester" [tiab] OR "intra-tester" [tiab] OR "interobserver" [tiab] OR "inter-observer" [tiab] OR "intraobserver" [tiab] OR "intra-observer" [tiab] OR "intertechician" [tiab] OR "inter-technician" [tiab] OR "intratechician" [tiab] OR "intra-technician" [tiab] OR "interexaminer" [tiab] OR "inter-examiner" [tiab] OR "intraexaminer" [tiab] OR "intra-examiner" [tiab] OR "interassay" [tiab] OR "inter-assay" [tiab] OR "intraassay" [tiab] OR "intra-assay" [tiab] OR "interindividual" [tiab] OR "inter-individual" [tiab] OR "intraindividual" [tiab] OR "intra-individual" [tiab] OR "interparticipant" [tiab] OR "inter-participant" [tiab] OR "intraparticipant" [tiab] OR "intra-participant" [tiab] OR "kappa" [tiab] OR "kappa's" [tiab] OR "kappas" [tiab] OR "repeatab*" [tw] OR (("replicab*" [tw] OR "repeated" [tw]) AND ("measure" [tw] OR "measures" [tw] OR "findings" [tw] OR "result" [tw] OR "results" [tw] OR "test" [tw] OR "tests" [tw])) OR "generaliza*" [tiab] OR "generalisa*" [tiab] OR "concordance" [tiab] OR ("intraclass" [tiab] AND "correlation*" [tiab]) OR "discriminative" [tiab] OR "known group" [tiab] OR "factor analysis" [tiab] OR "factor analyses" [tiab] OR "factor structure" [tiab] OR "factor structures" [tiab] OR "dimension*" [tiab] OR "subscale*" [tiab] OR ("multitrait" [tiab] AND "scaling" [tiab] AND ("analysis" [tiab] OR "analyses" [tiab])) OR "item discriminant" [tiab] OR "interscale correlation*" [tiab] OR "error" [tiab] OR "errors" [tiab] OR "individual variability" [tiab] OR

"interval variability"[tiab] OR "rate variability"[tiab] OR ("variability"[tiab] AND ("analysis"[tiab] OR "values"[tiab])) OR ("uncertainty"[tiab] AND ("measurement"[tiab] OR "measuring"[tiab])) OR "standard error of measurement"[tiab] OR "sensitive*"[tiab] OR "responsive*"[tiab] OR ("limit"[tiab] AND "detection"[tiab]) OR "minimal detectable concentration"[tiab] OR "interpretability*"[tiab] OR (("minimal"[tiab] OR "minimally"[tiab] OR "clinical"[tiab] OR "clinically"[tiab]) AND ("important"[tiab] OR "significant"[tiab] OR "detectable"[tiab]) AND ("change"[tiab] OR "difference"[tiab])) OR ("small*"[tiab] AND ("real"[tiab] OR "detectable"[tiab]) AND ("change"[tiab] OR "difference"[tiab])) OR "meaningful change"[tiab] OR "ceiling effect"[tiab] OR "floor effect"[tiab] OR "Item response model"[tiab] OR "IRT"[tiab] OR "Rasch"[tiab] OR "Differential item functioning"[tiab] OR "DIF"[tiab] OR "computer* adaptive testing"[tiab] OR "item bank"[tiab] OR "cross-cultural equivalence"[tiab])

BLOCK 3: Additional words specific to diagnostic accuracy

OR ("index test*"[tiab] OR "reference test*"[tiab] OR "reference standard*"[tiab] OR "gold standard"[tiab] OR "structured clinical interview"[tiab] OR "diagnostic accuracy"[tiab:~2] OR "DTA"[tiab] OR "predictive value*"[tiab] OR "PPV"[tiab] OR "NPV"[tiab] OR "positive predictive value"[tiab] OR "negative predictive value"[tiab] OR "likelihood ratio*"[tiab] OR "sensitivity"[ti] OR "specificity"[ti] OR "cut-off"[tiab] OR "cutoff"[tiab] OR "cut point"[tiab] OR "threshold score*"[tiab] OR "ROC"[tiab] OR "receiver* operating characteristic*"[tiab] OR "AUC"[tiab] OR "area* under the curve"[tiab] OR "case detection"[tiab] OR "case finding"[tiab] OR "classification*"[tiab])

BLOCK 4: Additional terms related to measurement properties

OR ("Patient Participation"[Mesh] OR "Patient* experience*"[tiab] OR "Patient* involvement*"[tiab] OR "Patient* input*"[tiab] OR "Patient* perception*"[tiab] OR "User* feedback*"[tiab] OR "Patient* feedback*"[tiab] OR "Cognitive interview*"[tiab] OR "Clinician* perception*"[tiab] OR "Pilot testing"[tiab] OR "Field testing"[tiab] OR "Focus Groups"[Mesh] OR "Focus group"[tiab] OR "Cognitive debriefing*"[tiab] OR "Expert* panel*"[tiab] OR "Expert* review*"[tiab] OR "Comprehensibility"[tiab] OR "Comprehensiveness"[tiab] OR "Item wording"[tiab] OR "Item evaluation"[tiab] OR "Item relevance"[tiab] OR "Item clarity"[tiab] OR "Item analysis*"[tiab] OR "Gold standard*"[tiab] OR "Area under curve"[tiab] OR "Area under a curve"[tiab] OR "Translation*"[tiab] OR "Measurement invariance"[tiab] OR "Cross-cultural"[tiab] OR "Back-translation"[tiab] OR "Forward-translation"[tiab] OR "Cross-group equivalence"[tiab] OR "Linguistic validation"[tiab] OR "Measurement equivalence"[tiab] OR "Semantic equivalence"[tiab] OR "Conceptual equivalence"[tiab] OR "measure* property*"[tiab] OR "CAT"[tiab] OR "Computerized Adaptive Testing"[Mesh] OR "computer adaptive testing"[tiab] OR "Scale development"[tiab] OR "Reflective model"[tiab] OR "Formative model"[tiab] OR "Measurement model"[tiab] OR "Classical test theory"[tiab] OR "Scoring algorithm"[tiab] OR "Instrument development"[tiab] OR "Questionnaire development"[tiab] OR

"McDonald* omega"[tiab] OR "Omega coefficient"[tiab] OR "Item-total correlation"[tiab] OR "Reference score"[tiab] OR "Perceived change"[tiab] OR "smallest worthwhile effect"[tiab] OR "LoA"[tiab] OR "SDC"[tiab] OR "MIC"[tiab] OR "intraclass correlation coefficient"[tiab] OR "ICC"[tiab] OR "item characteristic curve"[tiab] OR (("eigenvalue*"[tiab] OR "CFI"[tiab] OR "CFA"[tiab] OR "comparative fit index"[tiab] OR "TFI"[tiab] OR "tucker lewis index"[tiab] OR "RMSEA"[tiab] OR "root mean square error of approximation"[tiab] OR "SRMR"[tiab] OR "standardized root mean square residual"[tiab] OR "WRMR"[tiab] OR "weighted root mean square residual"[tiab] OR "ECV"[tiab] OR "explained common variance"[tiab] OR "PCA"[tiab] OR "component analy*"[tiab]) AND ("factor*"[tiab] OR "item*"[tiab])) OR "items factors"[tiab] OR "Item response theory"[tiab] OR "Kaiser criterion"[tiab] OR "Factor loadings"[tiab] OR "One-factor model"[tiab] OR "Two-factor model"[tiab] OR "Bifactor model"[tiab] OR "Bi-factor model"[tiab] OR "Localindependence"[tiab] OR "Monotonicity"[tiab] OR "Unidimensional"[tiab] OR ("item*"[tiab] AND ("correlation*"[tiab] OR "selection*"[tiab] OR "reduction*"[tiab])) OR "Floor effect*"[tiab] OR "Ceiling effect*"[tiab] OR "hypothes* test*"[tiab] OR "convergent"[tiab] OR "discriminant"[tiab] OR "known-groups"[tiab])

BLOCK 5: COSMIN exclusion filter with adaptations

NOT ("address"[Publication Type] OR "biography"[Publication Type] OR "case reports"[Publication Type] OR "comment"[Publication Type] OR "directory"[Publication Type] OR "editorial"[Publication Type] OR "festschrift"[Publication Type] OR "interview"[Publication Type] OR "lecture"[Publication Type] OR "legal case"[Publication Type] OR "legislation"[Publication Type] OR "letter"[Publication Type] OR "news"[Publication Type] OR "newspaper article"[Publication Type] OR "patient education handout"[Publication Type] OR "popular work"[Publication Type] OR "congress"[Publication Type] OR "consensus development conference"[Publication Type] OR "consensus development conference, nih"[Publication Type] OR "practice guideline"[Publication Type])

NOT ("animals"[MeSH Terms] NOT "humans"[MeSH Terms])

BLOCK 6: Publication date range

AND ("1995/01/01"[Date - Publication] : "2026/01/20"[Date - Publication])

Reference for the COSMIN filter (Terwee et al., 2009):

Terwee, C. B., Jansma, E. P., Riphagen, I. I., & de Vet, H. C. (2009). Development of a methodological PubMed search filter for finding studies on measurement properties of measurement instruments. *Quality of Life Research, 18*(8), 1115-1123.

Appendix D. Codebook for data extraction in Phase A (Living mapping of the evidence)

Category	Variable name	Variable definition	Permissible values
Study metadata	DOI	Digital Object Identifier	Alphanumeric DOI string
	Database identifier	Unique identifier assigned to the study by the database in which it is indexed (e.g., PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, Embase)	PMID (numeric), Web of Science Accession Number (alphanumeric), Embase ID (alphanumeric), or another database-specific identifier.
	Author	Surname of the first author of the study	First author surname followed by <i>et al.</i> (if applicable)
	Year of publication	Calendar year in which the study was published	Four-digit year (e.g., 2018)
	Journal	Name of the journal in which the article was published	Alphanumeric
	Article ID	Unique identifier assigned to the article within the review	Review-assigned article ID (Alphanumeric string)
	Sample ID	Unique identifier assigned within the review to each unique sample in the article (if multiple samples)	Review-assigned sample ID Not applicable
Study characteristics	Study methodological approach	Study methodological approach based on the nature of the data collected and the analytic methods used.	Quantitative Qualitative Mixed-methods Unclear – lack of reporting Unclear – don't know/don't understand

	Study design	Type of methodological design used in the study	Observational – Cross-sectional
			Observational – Longitudinal Prospective
			Observational – Longitudinal Retrospective
			Observational – Longitudinal (Timing Not Reported)
			Interventional – Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT)
			Interventional – Non-randomized Trial /quasi-experimental
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Inclusion criteria with threshold	Indicate if the participants of the study were included according to a continuous threshold	Yes
			No
Unclear – lack of reporting			
Unclear – don't know/don't understand			
PROM characteristics	Patient-reported outcome measure (PROM) used	Name of the PROM used in the study that is within the scope of this review (If a study uses more than one eligible PROM, a separate data-extraction row will be completed for each PROM)	GAD7 (7-item anxiety scale)
			PHQ9 (9-item depression scale)
			RCADS 25
			WHODAS 36-item
			WHODAS 12-item (short form)

			WHODAS 12+24-item
	Scoring computation method (only for WHODAS)	Method used to calculate WHODAS 2.0 scores: simple (unweighted sum), complex (IRT-weighted)	Simple scoring
			Complex scoring
			Not applicable
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Item wording modifications	Indicate whether the item wording has been modified from the original validated version of the instrument	Yes
			No
	Detail item wording modifications	Specify which changes were made to the item wording	Alphanumeric string
			Not applicable
	Response scoring modifications	Indicate whether the response scoring has been modified from the original validated version of the instrument	Yes
			No
	Detail response scoring modifications	Specify which changes were made to the response scoring	Alphanumeric string
			Not applicable
	Other PROM 1	Name of other instrument used in the study (to be completed if the study assessed any measurement property of another listed instrument in addition to the main eligible PROM)	GAD2 (2-item anxiety screener)
			PHQ2 (2-item depression screener)
			PHQ4 (4-item combined anxiety/depression screener)
PHQ5 (5-item short form)			

			PHQ8 (8-item depression scale (no suicidality item))
			RCADS 11
			RCADS 25
			RCADS 47
			WHODAS 36-item
			WHODAS 12-item (short form)
			WHODAS 12+24-item
			Other (specify)
			Not applicable
	Other PROM 1 (other)	Specify the name of the instrument when “Other (specify)” is selected for the variable Other PROM 1	Alphanumeric string
			Not applicable
	Other PROM 2	Name of other instrument used in the study (to be completed if the study assessed any measurement property of another listed instrument in addition to the main eligible PROM)	GAD2 (2-item anxiety screener)
			PHQ2 (2-item depression screener)
			PHQ4 (4-item combined anxiety/depression screener)
			PHQ5 (5-item short form)
PHQ8 (8-item depression scale (no suicidality item))			
RCADS 11			

			RCADS 25
			RCADS 47
			WHODAS 36-item
			WHODAS 12-item (short form)
			WHODAS 12+24-item
			Other (specify)
			Not applicable
	Other PROM 2 (other)	Specify the name of the instrument when “Other (specify)” is selected for the variable Other PROM 2	Alphanumeric string
			Not applicable
	Administration mode	Mode of administration indicating the informant of the scale	Self-reported version
			Caregiver report version (RCADS only)
			Interviewer version eliciting patient perspective
	Completion assistance	If the respondent requires assistance to complete the scale (without judgement or influence of the person assisting the application of the instrument), which type of assistance is provided to the target individual (informant) during completion of the scale	No assistance
			Interviewer-assisted
			Caregiver-assisted
Clinician-assisted			
Other (specify)			
Completion assistance (other)	Description of the type of completion assistance when “Other (specify)” is selected for the variable Completion assistance	Alphanumeric string	
		Not applicable	

	Medium of administration	Format or medium used to deliver the scale	Paper and pencil
			Digital device (any)
			Telephone interview
			Other (specify)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Medium of administration (other)	Description of the medium of administration when "Other (specify)" is selected for the variable Medium of administration	Alphanumeric string
			Not applicable
	Purpose of using the scale	Context of use of the PROM in which the measurement properties were evaluated	Diagnostic/screening
			Outcome assessment
			Other (specify)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
Language	Language in which the PROM is administered (as reported in the article)	Alphanumeric string	
		Unclear – lack of reporting	
		Unclear – don't know/don't understand	
Participants' characteristics	Description of the study sample	Description of the included study sample as shown in the article	Alphanumeric string
			Adults

	Age group of the study sample	Age category of the study sample as reported in the article, based on the age range or mean age of participants	Adolescents
			Adults and adolescents
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Sample size	Total number of participants included in the study/analysis	Integer value (N)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Minimum age (inclusion criteria)	Lower eligible age threshold	Age in years
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Maximum age (inclusion criteria)	Upper eligible age threshold	Age in years
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Minimum age (study sample)	Youngest age among participants included in the study	Age in years
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Maximum age (study sample)	Oldest age among participants included in the study	Age in years
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand

	Mean age of the study sample	Mean (average) age of the study sample	Numeric value (years)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Age standard deviation of the study sample	Standard deviation of age within the study sample	Numeric value (years)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Median age of the study sample	Median age within the study sample	Numeric value (years)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Number of male participants	Total number of male participants included in the study	Integer value (N)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Number of female participants	Total number of female participants included in the study	Integer value (N)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Sex distribution	Percentage of study participants who are female, as reported or calculable from the study (use the proportion reported by the authors or calculate it from provided sex distribution data when available)	Alphanumeric string. Percentage of male and female participants
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand

	Gender distribution	Percentage of participants categorized by gender identity (e.g., man, woman, non-binary), if defined or implied in the study, based on self-identification or explicit gender measures	Alphanumeric string. Percentage of participants self-identified as man, woman, non-binary or other (specify the percentage for each reported gender).
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Type of population	General classification of the population studied	Clinical (physical health conditions)
			Clinical (mental health conditions)
			Clinical (substance-use disorders)
			Healthy volunteer (with no diagnosed conditions)
			General population (community sample)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Category physical health condition 1	Primary category describing the physical health condition present in the study population, if applicable	Cardiovascular diseases (e.g., hypertension, coronary artery disease, heart failure, stroke)
			Metabolic and endocrine disorders (e.g., diabetes, obesity, metabolic syndrome, thyroid disorders)
			Respiratory diseases (e.g., asthma, COPD)
Neurological disorders (non-psychiatric) (e.g., Parkinson's disease, multiple sclerosis, epilepsy, migraine)			

			Musculoskeletal conditions (e.g., arthritis, chronic back pain, osteoporosis)
			Chronic pain conditions (e.g., fibromyalgia, chronic low back pain, neuropathic pain)
			Cancer / oncological conditions
			Autoimmune and inflammatory diseases (e.g., rheumatoid arthritis, lupus, inflammatory bowel disease)
			Gastrointestinal diseases (e.g., IBS, Crohn's disease, ulcerative colitis)
			Renal and urological diseases
			Chronic infectious diseases (e.g., HIV, hepatitis)
			Sensory impairments (e.g., visual or hearing impairment)
			Other physical health condition
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Name of the physical health condition 1	Specific physical health diagnosis or condition present in the study population, as reported by the authors	Alphanumeric string (e.g., Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus)
		Unclear – lack of reporting	
		Unclear – don't know/don't understand	

			Not applicable
Diagnostic basis physical health condition 1	Method used to determine the presence of the physical health condition among participants		Clinical diagnosis (medical record / clinician diagnosis)
			Standardized diagnostic criteria (e.g., ICD, ADA guidelines)
			Self-reported diagnosis
			Screening tool
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
Definition physical health condition 1	Operational or clinical definition of the physical health condition used in the study, including diagnostic criteria, assessment tools, thresholds, or author-provided descriptions		Alphanumeric string
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
Category physical health condition 2	Primary category describing an additional physical health condition present in the study population when multiple physical conditions are reported as comorbidities. If measurement properties are evaluated separately for different diseases using distinct participant samples, a		Cardiovascular diseases (e.g., hypertension, coronary artery disease, heart failure, stroke)
			Metabolic and endocrine disorders (e.g., diabetes, obesity, metabolic syndrome, thyroid disorders)
			Respiratory diseases (e.g., asthma, COPD)

		separate data-extraction row will be completed for each health condition.	Neurological disorders (non-psychiatric) (e.g., Parkinson's disease, multiple sclerosis, epilepsy, migraine)
			Musculoskeletal conditions (e.g., arthritis, chronic back pain, osteoporosis)
			Chronic pain conditions (e.g., fibromyalgia, chronic low back pain, neuropathic pain)
			Cancer / oncological conditions
			Autoimmune and inflammatory diseases (e.g., rheumatoid arthritis, lupus, inflammatory bowel disease)
			Gastrointestinal diseases (e.g., IBS, Crohn's disease, ulcerative colitis)
			Renal and urological diseases
			Chronic infectious diseases (e.g., HIV, hepatitis)
			Sensory impairments (e.g., visual or hearing impairment)
			Other physical health condition
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
Name of the physical health condition 2		Alphanumeric string (e.g., Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus)	

		Specific physical health diagnosis or condition present in the study population, as reported by the authors	Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Diagnostic basis physical health condition 2	Method used to determine the presence of the physical health condition among participants	Clinical diagnosis (medical record / clinician diagnosis)
			Standardized diagnostic criteria (e.g., ICD, ADA guidelines)
			Self-reported diagnosis
			Screening tool
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Definition physical health condition 2	Operational or clinical definition of the physical health condition used in the study, including diagnostic criteria, assessment tools, thresholds, or author-provided descriptions	Alphanumeric string
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Category physical health condition 3	Primary category describing an additional physical health condition present in the study population when multiple physical conditions are reported as comorbidities. If measurement properties are evaluated separately for different diseases using distinct participant samples, a	Cardiovascular diseases (e.g., hypertension, coronary artery disease, heart failure, stroke)
Metabolic and endocrine disorders (e.g., diabetes, obesity, metabolic syndrome, thyroid disorders)			

		<p>separate data-extraction row will be completed for each health condition</p>	<table border="1"> <tr> <td data-bbox="1352 189 1892 252">Respiratory diseases (e.g., asthma, COPD)</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1352 252 1892 387">Neurological disorders (non-psychiatric) (e.g., Parkinson's disease, multiple sclerosis, epilepsy, migraine)</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1352 387 1892 483">Musculoskeletal conditions (e.g., arthritis, chronic back pain, osteoporosis)</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1352 483 1892 579">Chronic pain conditions (e.g., fibromyalgia, chronic low back pain, neuropathic pain)</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1352 579 1892 641">Cancer / oncological conditions</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1352 641 1892 777">Autoimmune and inflammatory diseases (e.g., rheumatoid arthritis, lupus, inflammatory bowel disease)</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1352 777 1892 873">Gastrointestinal diseases (e.g., IBS, Crohn's disease, ulcerative colitis)</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1352 873 1892 935">Renal and urological diseases</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1352 935 1892 997">Chronic infectious diseases (e.g., HIV, hepatitis)</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1352 997 1892 1093">Sensory impairments (e.g., visual or hearing impairment)</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1352 1093 1892 1155">Other physical health condition</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1352 1155 1892 1217">Unclear – lack of reporting</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1352 1217 1892 1279">Unclear – don't know/don't understand</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1352 1279 1892 1342">Not applicable</td> </tr> </table>	Respiratory diseases (e.g., asthma, COPD)	Neurological disorders (non-psychiatric) (e.g., Parkinson's disease, multiple sclerosis, epilepsy, migraine)	Musculoskeletal conditions (e.g., arthritis, chronic back pain, osteoporosis)	Chronic pain conditions (e.g., fibromyalgia, chronic low back pain, neuropathic pain)	Cancer / oncological conditions	Autoimmune and inflammatory diseases (e.g., rheumatoid arthritis, lupus, inflammatory bowel disease)	Gastrointestinal diseases (e.g., IBS, Crohn's disease, ulcerative colitis)	Renal and urological diseases	Chronic infectious diseases (e.g., HIV, hepatitis)	Sensory impairments (e.g., visual or hearing impairment)	Other physical health condition	Unclear – lack of reporting	Unclear – don't know/don't understand	Not applicable
Respiratory diseases (e.g., asthma, COPD)																	
Neurological disorders (non-psychiatric) (e.g., Parkinson's disease, multiple sclerosis, epilepsy, migraine)																	
Musculoskeletal conditions (e.g., arthritis, chronic back pain, osteoporosis)																	
Chronic pain conditions (e.g., fibromyalgia, chronic low back pain, neuropathic pain)																	
Cancer / oncological conditions																	
Autoimmune and inflammatory diseases (e.g., rheumatoid arthritis, lupus, inflammatory bowel disease)																	
Gastrointestinal diseases (e.g., IBS, Crohn's disease, ulcerative colitis)																	
Renal and urological diseases																	
Chronic infectious diseases (e.g., HIV, hepatitis)																	
Sensory impairments (e.g., visual or hearing impairment)																	
Other physical health condition																	
Unclear – lack of reporting																	
Unclear – don't know/don't understand																	
Not applicable																	

	Name of the physical health condition 3	Specific physical health diagnosis or condition present in the study population, as reported by the authors	Alphanumeric string (e.g., Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Diagnostic basis physical health condition 3	Method used to determine the presence of the physical health condition among participants	Clinical diagnosis (medical record / clinician diagnosis)
			Standardized diagnostic criteria (e.g., ICD, ADA guidelines)
			Self-reported diagnosis
			Screening tool
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Definition physical health condition 3	Operational or clinical definition of the physical health condition used in the study, including diagnostic criteria, assessment tools, thresholds, or author-provided descriptions	Alphanumeric string
			Unclear – lack of reporting
Unclear – don't know/don't understand			
Not applicable			
Category mental health condition 1		Depressive disorders (e.g., major depressive disorder, dysthymia)	

		Primary category describing the mental health condition present in the study population, if applicable	Anxiety disorders (e.g., generalized anxiety disorder, panic disorder, phobias)
			Stress-related and trauma-related disorders (e.g., PTSD, adjustment disorder)
			Bipolar and related disorders
			Psychotic disorders (e.g., schizophrenia, schizoaffective disorder)
			Neurodevelopmental disorders (e.g., ADHD, autism spectrum disorder)
			Eating disorders (e.g., anorexia nervosa, bulimia nervosa, binge-eating disorder)
			Personality disorders
			Cognitive disorders / dementia
			Sleep-wake disorders (e.g., insomnia)
			Other mental health condition
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
Name of the mental health condition 1	Specific mental health diagnosis or condition present in the study population, as reported by the authors	Alphanumeric string (e.g., major depressive disorder)	
		Unclear – lack of reporting	
		Unclear – don't know/don't understand	

			Not applicable
Diagnostic basis mental health condition 1	Method used to determine the presence of the mental health condition among participants		Clinical diagnosis (medical record / clinician diagnosis)
			Standardized diagnostic criteria (e.g., DSM, ICD)
			Self-reported diagnosis
			Screening tool
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
Definition mental health condition 1	Operational or clinical definition of the mental health condition used in the study, including diagnostic criteria, assessment tools, thresholds, or author-provided descriptions		Alphanumeric string
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
Category mental health condition 2	Primary category describing an additional mental health condition present in the study population when multiple mental health conditions are reported as comorbidities. If measurement properties are evaluated separately for different diseases using distinct participant samples, a separate data-extraction row will be completed for each health condition		Depressive disorders (e.g., major depressive disorder, dysthymia)
			Anxiety disorders (e.g., generalized anxiety disorder, panic disorder, phobias)
			Stress-related and trauma-related disorders (e.g., PTSD, adjustment disorder)
			Bipolar and related disorders

			Psychotic disorders (e.g., schizophrenia, schizoaffective disorder)
			Neurodevelopmental disorders (e.g., ADHD, autism spectrum disorder)
			Eating disorders (e.g., anorexia nervosa, bulimia nervosa, binge-eating disorder)
			Personality disorders
			Cognitive disorders / dementia
			Sleep-wake disorders (e.g., insomnia)
			Other mental health condition
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Name of the mental health condition 2	Specific mental health diagnosis or condition present in the study population, as reported by the authors	Alphanumeric string (e.g., major depressive disorder)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
Not applicable			
Diagnostic basis mental health condition 2	Method used to determine the presence of the mental health condition among participants	Clinical diagnosis (medical record / clinician diagnosis)	
		Standardized diagnostic criteria (e.g., DSM, ICD)	

			Self-reported diagnosis
			Screening tool
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Definition mental health condition 2	Operational or clinical definition of the mental health condition used in the study, including diagnostic criteria, assessment tools, thresholds, or author-provided descriptions	Alphanumeric string
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Category mental health condition 3	Primary category describing an additional mental health condition present in the study population when multiple mental health conditions are reported as comorbidities. If measurement properties are evaluated separately for different diseases using distinct participant samples, a separate data-extraction row will be completed for each health condition	Depressive disorders (e.g., major depressive disorder, dysthymia)
			Anxiety disorders (e.g., generalized anxiety disorder, panic disorder, phobias)
			Stress-related and trauma-related disorders (e.g., PTSD, adjustment disorder)
			Bipolar and related disorders
			Psychotic disorders (e.g., schizophrenia, schizoaffective disorder)
			Neurodevelopmental disorders (e.g., ADHD, autism spectrum disorder)
Eating disorders (e.g., anorexia nervosa, bulimia nervosa, binge-eating disorder)			

			Personality disorders
			Cognitive disorders / dementia
			Sleep-wake disorders (e.g., insomnia)
			Other mental health condition
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Name of the mental health condition 3	Specific mental health diagnosis or condition present in the study population, as reported by the authors	Alphanumeric string (e.g., major depressive disorder)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Diagnostic basis mental health condition 3	Method used to determine the presence of the mental health condition among participants	Clinical diagnosis (medical record / clinician diagnosis)
			Standardized diagnostic criteria (e.g., DSM, ICD)
			Self-reported diagnosis
			Screening tool
Unclear – lack of reporting			
Unclear – don't know/don't understand			

			Not applicable
	Definition mental health condition 3	Operational or clinical definition of the mental health condition used in the study, including diagnostic criteria, assessment tools, thresholds, or author-provided descriptions	Alphanumeric string
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Category substance-use disorder 1	Primary category describing the substance-use disorder present in the study population, if applicable	Alcohol use disorder
			Tobacco / nicotine use disorder
			Cannabis use disorder
			Opioid use disorder
			Stimulant use disorder (e.g., cocaine, amphetamines, methamphetamine)
			Sedative, hypnotic, or anxiolytic use disorder
			Polysubstance use disorder
			Other substance-use disorder
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Name of the substance-use disorder 1	Specific substance-use disorder present in the study population, as reported by the authors	Alphanumeric string (e.g., alcohol abuse disorder)
			Unclear – lack of reporting

			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Diagnostic basis substance-use disorder 1	Method used to determine the presence of the substance-use disorder among participants	Clinical diagnosis (medical record / clinician diagnosis)
			Standardized diagnostic criteria (e.g., DSM, ICD)
			Self-reported diagnosis
			Screening tool
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Definition substance-use disorder 1	Operational or clinical definition of the substance-use disorder used in the study, including diagnostic criteria, assessment tools, thresholds, or author-provided descriptions	Alphanumeric string
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Category substance-use disorder 2	Primary category describing an additional substance-use disorder present in the study population when multiple substance-use disorders are reported as coexistent. If measurement properties are evaluated separately for different substance-use disorders using distinct participant	Alcohol use disorder
			Tobacco / nicotine use disorder
			Cannabis use disorder
			Opioid use disorder

		samples, a separate data-extraction row will be completed for each disorder	Stimulant use disorder (e.g., cocaine, amphetamines, methamphetamine)
			Sedative, hypnotic, or anxiolytic use disorder
			Polysubstance use disorder
			Other substance-use disorder
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Name of the substance-use disorder 2	Specific substance-use disorder present in the study population, as reported by the authors	Alphanumeric string (e.g., alcohol abuse disorder)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Diagnostic basis substance-use disorder 2	Method used to determine the presence of the substance-use disorder among participants	Clinical diagnosis (medical record / clinician diagnosis)
			Standardized diagnostic criteria (e.g., DSM, ICD)
Self-reported diagnosis			
Screening tool			
Unclear – lack of reporting			
Unclear – don't know/don't understand			

			Not applicable
Definition substance-use disorder 2	Operational or clinical definition of the substance-use disorder used in the study, including diagnostic criteria, assessment tools, thresholds, or author-provided descriptions		Alphanumeric string
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
Category substance-use disorder 3	Primary category describing an additional substance-use disorder present in the study population when multiple substance-use disorders are reported as coexistent. If measurement properties are evaluated separately for different substance-use disorders using distinct participant samples, a separate data-extraction row will be completed for each disorder		Alcohol use disorder
			Tobacco / nicotine use disorder
			Cannabis use disorder
			Opioid use disorder
			Stimulant use disorder (e.g., cocaine, amphetamines, methamphetamine)
			Sedative, hypnotic, or anxiolytic use disorder
			Polysubstance use disorder
			Other substance-use disorder
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Not applicable		
Name of the substance-use disorder 3	Specific substance-use disorder present in the study population, as reported by the authors		Alphanumeric string (e.g., alcohol abuse disorder)
			Unclear – lack of reporting

			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
Diagnostic basis substance-use disorder 3	Method used to determine the presence of the substance-use disorder among participants	Clinical diagnosis (medical record / clinician diagnosis)	
		Standardized diagnostic criteria (e.g., DSM, ICD)	
		Self-reported diagnosis	
		Screening tool	
		Unclear – lack of reporting	
		Unclear – don't know/don't understand	
		Not applicable	
Definition substance-use disorder 3	Operational or clinical definition of the substance-use disorder used in the study, including diagnostic criteria, assessment tools, thresholds, or author-provided descriptions	Alphanumeric string	
		Unclear – lack of reporting	
		Unclear – don't know/don't understand	
		Not applicable	
Specific demographics	Identification of specific demographic subgroups targeted in the study	Veterans	
		LGBTQIA+	
		Migrants	
		Other (specify)	
Geographical setting		Country or countries	

		Geographic location where the study was conducted	Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Healthcare setting level	Level of healthcare system in which the study was conducted	Primary care
			Secondary care
			Tertiary care
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Patient setting	Care context in which participants received services or were studied	Outpatient
			Inpatient
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
PROM construct and assessed measurement properties in the study	PROM construct	Construct that the PROM is intended to assess, as explicitly stated by the study authors	Alphanumeric string. Construct description using authors' wording (e.g., quality of life, physical functioning, pain intensity, mental health, symptom severity, etc.)
	Content validity*	The degree to which the content of a PROM is an adequate reflection of the construct to be measured.	Yes – reported results
			Unclear – lack of reporting

			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Structural validity*	The degree to which the scores of a PROM are an adequate reflection of the dimensionality of the construct to be measured.	Yes – reported results
			Not assessed
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Internal consistency*	The degree of the interrelatedness among the items.	Yes – reported results
			Not assessed
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Cross-cultural validity / measurement invariance*	The degree to which the performance of the items on a translated or culturally adapted PROM are an adequate reflection of the performance of the items of the original version of the PROM.	Yes – reported results
			Not assessed
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Reliability*	The extent to which scores for respondents who have not changed are the same for repeated measurement under several conditions: e.g., using different sets of items from the same PROM (internal consistency); over time (test-retest); by different persons on the same occasion (inter-rater); or by the same persons (i.e., raters or responders) on different occasions (intra-rater).	Yes – reported results
			Not assessed
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
Measurement error*		Yes – reported results	

		The systematic and random error of a respondent's score that is not attributed to true changes in the construct to be measured.	Not assessed	
			Unclear – lack of reporting	
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand	
	Criterion validity*	Criterion validity refers to the degree to which PROM scores are an adequate reflection of a reference standard (gold standard).		Yes – reported results
				Not assessed
				Unclear – lack of reporting
				Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Comparator instrument for criterion validity	If results for criterion validity are reported, specify which instrument has been used as comparator		Alphanumeric string.
				Not applicable
	Hypothesis testing for construct validity*	The degree to which the scores of a PROM are consistent with hypotheses (with regard to relationships to scores of other instruments, or differences between relevant groups) based on the assumption that the PROM validly measures the construct to be measured.		Yes – reported results
				Not assessed
				Unclear – lack of reporting
				Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Comparator instrument for hypothesis testing for construct validity	If results for hypothesis testing for construct validity are reported, specify which instrument has been used as comparator		Alphanumeric string.
				Not applicable
	Responsiveness*	The ability of a PROM to detect change over time in the construct to be measured.		Yes – reported results
				Not assessed
				Unclear – lack of reporting
				Unclear – don't know/don't understand

	Comparator instrument for Responsiveness	If results for Responsiveness are reported, specify which instrument has been used as comparator	Alphanumeric string.
			Not applicable
Other properties of the measurement tools	Feasibility*	Ease of application of the PROM in its intended context of use, given constraints such as time or money.	Yes – reported results
			Not assessed
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don’t know/don’t understand
	Interpretability*	The degree to which one can assign qualitative meaning - that is, clinical or commonly understood connotations – to a PROM’s quantitative scores or change in scores.	Yes – reported results
			Not assessed
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don’t know/don’t understand
	Acceptability	How respondents perceive the experience of completing the scale, e.g., perceived intrusiveness, burden, potential harms or benefits.	Yes – reported results
			Not assessed
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don’t know/don’t understand
Involvement of contributors with lived experiences	Involvement of lived-experience contributors	Indicate whether individuals with lived experience actively contributed to the study.	Yes
			No
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don’t know/don’t understand

* Definition derived from the COSMIN taxonomy, as specified in the COSMIN 2.0 guidelines (Mokkink et al., 2024).